

Catalogue
of the
Bailiffs' Records
of
Nyland
(1540–1634)

Seppo Eskola

Covering shelf marks

KA 2918 – 3667

in the archival collection

Voudintilit

at the Finnish National Archives in Helsinki

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Helsinki, January 2023

Seppo Eskola

Introduction

Over the course of the sixteenth century Sweden developed into a centrally led nation state. At the heart of this process was the expansion of central and local administrative structures, especially those regarding taxation. As the new structures took hold, detailed cameral bookkeeping practices were implemented nation-wide and bookkeeping records began to be produced on an unprecedented scale. Gradually, this process resulted in tens of thousands of tax records from all over the country being accumulated and stored in Stockholm.

Today, these records – commonly known as *Fogderäkenskaper* (Swe) or *Voudintilit* (Fin), translated here as the *Bailiffs' records* – are preserved at the Swedish and Finnish National Archives. The Finnish collection consists of nine sections, one for each of eight Finnish provinces and a general section. The Finnish records are exceptionally well-preserved, and the collection covers nearly half a million folios divided into 7 291 shelf marks. All Finnish records have been digitized from microfilm (as well as some from originals) and are available online through the Finnish National Archives.

The collections are vast, and catalogues are essential for navigating them. Yet, the only full catalogue on the Finnish collection intended for scholarly use dates to the 1850's. This catalogue was produced by Dr. Edward Grönblad who oversaw the organizing of the Finnish collection after it was moved to Finland from Sweden. The catalogue has served many generations of scholars, but clearly no longer meets the requirements of modern scholarship. The only other modern catalogue on the Finnish material is by the present writer, covering the records of the Duchy of Johan, located in south-western Finland in 1556–1563.¹

The present catalogue

The catalogue at hand covers the section for the province of Nyland in the Finnish collection of the *Bailiffs' records*. The province of Nyland consisted of *Raseborgs län* in the west and *Borgå län* in the east. *Kymmenegårds län* was situated between Nyland and Karelen, and its records have been inconsistently divided between the archival series of these two provinces. Therefore, some of them are included here, while others are not. All in all, the records found in the series for Nyland consist of 780 shelf marks or c. 58 400 folios, making up roughly ten percent of the whole Helsinki collection (see further on for more details).

The structure of the catalogue is as follows: the cameral records are listed in the order of their shelf marks with headlines added for each year as well as for each bailiwick and bailiff. The shelf marks are then further divided into smaller units of bookkeeping when appropriate. The structure of the local administration is key for perceiving the material clearly. The bailiwick numbers provided are based on Johan Axel Almquist's classical work *Den civila lokalförvaltningen i Sverige 1523–1630*, which can be found online for consultation.² Almquist's bailiwick tables for Nyland have also been reproduced here, and

¹ The catalogue was published as an appendix to the dissertation: Eskola, Seppo, *Archives, Accounting, and Accountability: Cameral Bookkeeping in Mid-Sixteenth-Century Sweden and the Duchy of Johan (1556–1563)*. University of Helsinki, 2020. <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-951-51-6872-6>.

² Almquist, J.A., *Den civila lokalförvaltningen i Sverige 1523–1630*. I–IV. Stockholm: P.A. Nordstedt och Söner 1917–1923 (I: 1917, II: 1919, III: 1917–1922, and IV: 1922–1923). The work has been digitized and

they provide an overview of the structure of bailiwicks in Nyland. The tables can be found following this introduction.

The catalogue has been written in English as it follows the same format as the aforementioned catalogue on the records of the Duchy of Johan. Some bookkeeping terms and notes, however, are given in the original Swedish of the sources. There is no settled terminology for discussing the Bailiffs' records in English, and the choices that have been made follow the terminology established in the present writer's dissertation *Archives, Accounting, and Accountability: Cameral Bookkeeping in Mid-Sixteenth-Century Sweden and the Duchy of Johan (1556–1563)*.³

To an extent, the catalogue at hand is a work-in-progress. It has been written over time with some parts of the collection receiving more attention than others and is published now with the intent to later produce an updated version.⁴ Alongside general improvements, the updated version is intended to incorporate information on the medieval parchment covers of the records.⁵ Hopefully, at its current stage, the catalogue will provide a useful tool for navigating the material, finding specific information, and contextualising records as parts of wider sets of bookkeeping. Feedback and suggestions for changes are welcome.

The records of Nyland

The records of Nyland cover slightly over ten percent of the Finnish Bailiffs' records. The following tables and diagrams aim to contextualize the material as part of the Helsinki collection as well as visualise its internal structure. The diagrams are based either on shelf marks or folios, both of which provide one point of view to the material. The shelf marks – despite dating to the nineteenth century – are rooted in sixteenth- and seventeenth-century practices as each shelf mark generally corresponds to a now-removed parchment cover. Typically, one shelf mark contains several units of bookkeeping, but one shelf mark can also correspond to just one unit or even only a part of one. Folios provide a more accurate image of the overall volume of bookkeeping but can also be misleading as they do not account for empty folios or different folio sizes and writing styles.

More information on the bailiffs' records can be found, e.g., through the brief list of selected literature following this introduction.

placed online by the ERC project *Books of the Medieval Parish Church* (National Library of Finland), see <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2022033026181>.

³ See footnote 1.

⁴ Generally, earlier records have received more attention than later ones, records from the seventeenth century having been scrutinized least.

⁵ As is well known, the covers of the Finnish collection were separated from the records in the nineteenth century and can now be found at the Finnish National Library. Work on re-establishing a connection between the covers and the records is currently being undertaken as part of the ERC project *Books of the Medieval Parish Church* (2021–2025), hosted by the National Library and led by Dr. Jaakko Tahkokallio. For more on the project, see: <https://www2.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/books-of-the-medieval-parish-church>.

Tables and diagrams on the Helsinki collection

The figures are based on data collected from existing catalogues. They provide a good overall picture of the material but include some uncertainty (especially the figures on folia).

Table 1

Province	Shelf marks	%
Åland	332	4,6 %
Österbotten	502	6,9 %
Satakunda	694	9,5 %
Savolax	696	9,5 %
General	750	10,3 %
Nyland	780	10,7 %
Tavastland	889	12,2 %
Karelen	1 166	16,0 %
Egentliga Finland	1 482	20,3 %
	7 291	100,0 %

Table 2

Province	Folia	%
Åland	19 598	3,9 %
Österbotten	36 778	7,4 %
Satakunda	43 815	8,8 %
Savolax	43 934	8,8 %
Tavastland	54 264	10,9 %
Nyland	58 382	11,7 %
General	59 495	11,9 %
Karelen	85 810	17,2 %
Egentliga Finland	95 940	19,3 %
	498 016	100,0 %

Diagram 1

Diagram 2

Table 3

Province	Shelf marks	Folia
Raseborgs län	392	27 693
Borgå län	295	23 612
Kymmenegårds län	89	6 959
Entire Nyland	4	118
	780	58 382

Diagram 3

Diagram 4

Diagram 5

Archival collections and selected literature

Archival collections containing the Bailiffs' records

Kansallisarkisto, Helsinki

Voudintilit (KA 1 – 6 807)

See also the nineteenth-century archival catalogues

arkisto.fi

Riksarkivet, Stockholm

Landskapshandlingarna and several other collections

riksarkivet.se

Selected literature

Almquist, Johan Axel, *Den civila lokalförvaltningen i Sverige 1523–1630*. I–IV. Stockholm: P.A. Nordstedt och Söner 1917–1923 (I: 1917, II: 1919, III: 1917–1922, and IV: 1922–1923). <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2022033026181>.

Brunius, Jan, "Landskapshandlingarna i Riksarkivet". *Arkiv, samhälle och forskning* 2000:I, 7–27.

Brunius, Jan, *Vasatidens samhälle. En vägledning till arkiven 1520–1620 i Riksarkivet*. Stockholm: Riksarkivet 2010.

Edwards, J. R. and Walker, S. P. (eds.), *The Routledge Companion to Accounting History*. New York: Routledge 2009.

Eskola, Seppo, *Archives, Accounting, and Accountability – Cameral Bookkeeping in Mid-Sixteenth-Century Sweden and the Duchy of Johan (1556–1563)*. Helsingin yliopisto, 2020. <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-951-51-6872-6>.

Kerkkonen, Martti, *Suomen arkistolaitos Haminan rauhasta maan itsenäistymiseen*. Helsinki: Valtionarkisto 1988.

Renvall, Pentti, *Historiantutkimuksen työmenetelmät*. Porvoo–Helsinki: WSOY 1947.

Bailiwick tables

The following tables are based on those published by J.A. Almquist in the third volume of his work *Den civila lokalförvaltningen i Sverige 1523–1630* (I–IV 1917–1923). Some simplifications have been made and some information not directly concerning the bailiwicks has been omitted. The original tables are available online as part of Almquist's study (see 'Literature'). The numbers used in the tables refer to individual bailiwicks and show their structure at any given time. Detailed descriptions can be found in the second volume of Almquist's work. The highlight colours serve only as visual aids.

I. 1540–1569

Raseborgs län																	
	Raseborg		Ekenäs stad & gård	Tenala socken	Karis socken	Pojo		Lojo socken	Laxpojo gård	Victis socken	Ingo socken	Sjundeå		Kyrkslätt socken	Esbo		
	slottet	ladu- gården				socken	(Näs) gård					socken	gård		socken	gård	
1540	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	321	~	~	321	321	~	321	321	~	1540
1541	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	331	321	321	~	321	321	~	1541
1542	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	331	321	321	~	321	321	~	1542
1543	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	331	321	321	~	321	321	~	1543
1544	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	331	321	321	~	321	321	~	1544
1545	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	331	321	321	~	321	321	~	1545
1546	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	331	321	321	~	321	321	~	1546
1547	321	~	~	~	321	321	~	~	~	331	321	321	~	321	321	~	1547
1548	321	~	~	~	321	321	~	~	~	332	321	321	~	321	321	~	1548
1549	321	~	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	332	321	321	~	321	321	~	1549
1550	321	321	~	~	321	~	~	~	~	332	321	321	~	321	321	~	1550
1551	321	321	~	~	321	~	~	321	~	332	321	321	~	321	321	~	1551
1552	321	321	~	~	321	~	~	321	~	332	321	321	~	321	321	~	1552
1553	321	321	~	~	321	~	~	321	~	321	321	321	~	321	321	~	1553
1554	~	321	~	~	321	~	~	321	~	321	321	321	~	321	321	~	1554
1555	~	321	~	321	321	321	~	321	~	321	321	321	~	321	321	~	1555
1556	~	321	~	321	321	321	~	323	323	323	324	324	324	324	328	~	1556
1557	~	321	~	321	321	321	321	323	323	323	324	324	324	324	324	325	1557
1558	~	321	~	321	321	321	326	323	323	323	321	321	324	321	321	325	1558
1559	~	321	~	321	321	321	321	323	323	323	321	321	~	321	321	321	1559
1560	~	322	321	321	321	321	326	323	323	323	321	321	~	321	321	325	1560
1561	~	322	321	321	321	321	326	323	323	323	321	321	~	321	321	325	1561
1562	~	322	321	321	321	321	326	323	323	323	321	321	~	321	321	325	1562
1563	~	322	321	321	321	321	326	321	~	321	321	321	~	321	321	325	1563
1564	~	322	321	321	321	321	326	321	~	327	321	321	~	327	327	327	1564
1565	~	322	321	321	321	321	326	321	~	327	321	321	~	327	327	327	1565
1566	~	321	321	321	321	321	~	321	~	327	321	321	~	327	327	327	1566
1567	~	321	321	321	321	321	~	321	~	327	321	321	~	327	327	327	1567
1568	~	321	321	321	321	321	~	321	~	327	321	321	~	327	327	327	1568
1569	~	321	321	321	321	321	~	~	~	327	321	321	~	327	327	327	1569

327: see also Borgå län

328: see also Borgå län

331: see also Tavastland (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 120–127)

332: see also Tavastland (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 120–127)

I. 1540–1569

	Borgå län								Kymmenegårds län					
	Helsinge		Sibbo socken		Borgå		Perno socken		Artjärvi fjärding	Elimä fjärding	Pyttis socken		Kymmene gård	
	socken	Helsingfors gård	¾	Kaukjärvi fjärding	socken	gård	¾	Sävträsk fjärding			Mertelaks fjärding	¾		
1540	338	~	338	338	338	327	338	338	331	331	338	338	~	1540
1541	338	~	338	338	338	327	338	338	331	331	338	338	~	1541
1542	338	~	338	338	338	327	338	338	331	331	338	338	~	1542
1543	338	~	338	338	338	327	338	338	331	331	338	338	~	1543
1544	338	~	338	338	338	327	338	338	331	331	338	338	~	1544
1545	338	~	338	338	338	327	338	338	331	331	338	338	~	1545
1546	338	~	338	338	338	327	338	338	331	331	338	338	~	1546
1547	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	331	331	327	327	~	1547
1548	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	335	335	327	327	~	1548
1549	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	335	335	327	327	~	1549
1550	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	335	335	327	327	~	1550
1551	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	335	335	327	327	~	1551
1552	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	335	335	327	327	~	1552
1553	321	321	321	321	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	~	1553
1554	321	321	321	321	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	~	1554
1555	321	321	321	321	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	~	1555
1556	328	328	328	328	327	327	327	327	327	329	327	329	329	1556
1557	328	328	328	328	327	327	327	327	327	329	327	329	329	1557
1558	328	328	328	328	327	327	327	327	327	329	327	329	329	1558
1559	328	328	328	328	327	327	327	327	327	329	327	329	329	1559
1560	328	328	328	328	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	1560
1561	328	328	~	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	329	329	329	1561
1562	327	327	~	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	329	329	329	1562
1563	327	327	327	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	329	329	329	1563
1564	327	327	327	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	329	329	329	1564
1565	327	327	327	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	329	329	329	1565
1566	327	327	327	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	329	329	329	1566
1567	327	327	327	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	~	329	329	1567
1568	327	327	327	~	327	327	327	~	327	329	~	329	329	1568
1569	327	~	327	~	327	327	327	~	327	~	~	~	~	1569

321: see also Raseborgs län

331: see also Tavastland (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 120–127)

335: see also Tavastland (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 120–127)

338: see also Karelen (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 128–133)

II. 1570–1599

Raseborgs län																	
Raseborgs gård och socken	Ekenäs gård och stad	Ingo socken	Lojo socken				Karislojo kapellgåll	Pojo socken	Tenala socken		Sjundeå socken			Kyrksläatts och Esbo socknar	Esbo gård		
			Tötare bol	Hirvijoki, Koisijärvi och Vastelaks' bol	Övriga sex bol	Koskis och Maksjoki bol			Finnby bol	Övriga bol	Viks bol och två byar i böls bol	4 ½ bol	Övriga sex bol				
1570	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	321	321	x	321	321	327	327	1570
1571	x	321	x	321	x	x	x	321	321	321	321	x	x	321	327	327	1571
1572	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	303	303	303	303	x	x	327	327	325	1572
1573	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	303	303	303	303	x	x	327	327	325	1573
1574	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	321	321	321	321	x	x	321	321	325	1574
1575	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	321	321	321	321	x	x	321	321	325	1575
1576	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	321	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1576
1577	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	321	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1577
1578	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1578
1579	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1579
1580	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1580
1581	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1581
1582	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1582
1583	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1583
1584	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1584
1585	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1585
1586	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1586
1587	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1587
1588	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1588
1589	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	321	321	1589
1590	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	x	321	x	x	x	321	321	1590
1591	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	x	321	x	321	321	321	321	1591
1592	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	x	321	x	321	321	321	321	1592
1593	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	x	321	x	321	321	321	321	1593
1594	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	321	x	321	x	321	321	321	~	1594
1595	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	321	x	321	x	321	321	321	~	1595
1596	x	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	321	x	321	x	321	321	321	~	1596
1597	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	1597
1598	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	1598
1599	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	321	1599

303: see also Egentliga Finland (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 102–108)

II. 1570–1599

	Borgå län											Kymmenegårds län						
	Borgå gård	Viks ladugård	Helsingfors gård	Helsinge socken		Sibbo socken		Borgå socken		Perno socken		Pyttis socken		Elimä fjärding	Vekkelaks socken	Vederlaks socken		Kymmene gård
				Hoplaks och Clemetskogs fjärdingar	Viks och kyrke fjärdingar	Kaukjärvi fjärding	3/4	Mendze fjärding	3/4	Sävträsk fjärding	3/4	Mertelaks fjärding	3/4					
1570	327	327	327	327	327	x	327	327	327	x	327	x	329	329	329	329	~	1570
1571	327	327	327	327	327	x	327	327	327	x	327	x	329	329	329	329	~	1571
1572	325	325	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	342	338	1572
1573	325	325	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	342	338	1573
1574	325	325	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	338	1574
1575	325	325	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	338	1575
1576	x	~	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	338	1576
1577	x	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1577
1578	x	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1578
1579	x	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1579
1580	x	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1580
1581	x	327	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1581
1582	x	~	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1582
1583	x	~	~	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1583
1584	x	~	~	~	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1584
1585	x	~	~	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1585
1586	x	~	~	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1586
1587	x	~	328	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1587
1588	x	328	328	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1588
1589	x	327	327	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1589
1590	x	327	327	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1590
1591	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1591
1592	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	329	1592
1593	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	1593
1594	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	1594
1595	x	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	x	~	~	329	329	329	329	329	1595
1596	x	~	~	~	~	~	~	x	~	x	~	~	329	329	329	329	329	1596
1597	x	~	327	~	~	~	~	x	~	x	~	~	329	329	329	329	329	1597
1598	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	327	x	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	1598
1599	x	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	327	x	327	327	329	329	329	329	329	1599

338: see also Karelen (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 128–133)

342: see also Karelen (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 128–133)

III. 1600–1630

Raseborgs län																
Raseborgs slott, Ekenäs gård och stad	Karis och Ingo socknar	Tenala socken	Pojo socken				Karislojo kapellgåll	Lojo socken		Sjundeå socken		Kyrksläpps socken		Esbo socken	Esbo gård	
			Lappviks bol	Övriga delar	Kisko bol	Koskis och Ratis bol		Övriga delar	Hummerkila och Björn- träsk's bol	Övriga delar	Estby bol	Övriga delar				
1600	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	1600
1601	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	~	1601
1602	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	1602
1603	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	321	x	321	321	321	321	~	1603
1604	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	321	321	321	321	~	1604
1605	x	x	321	321	321	321	x	x	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	1605
1606	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	~	1606
1607	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	1607
1608	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	1608
1609	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	321	x	x	1609
1610	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	321	x	x	1610
1611	x	x	x	321	321	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	321	x	x	1611
1612	x	x	x	x	321	x	x	x	x	x	321	x	321	x	x	1612
1613	x	x	x	321	321	~	x	x	~	~	321	~	321	~	~	1613
1614	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	~	1614
1615	x	x	x	321	321	321	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	~	1615
1616	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	~	1616
1617	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	1617
1618	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	1618
1619	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	1619
1620	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	1620
1621	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	~	1621
1622	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1622
1623	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1623
1624	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1624
1625	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1625
1626	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1626
1627	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1627
1628	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1628
1629	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1629
1630	x	x	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	321	325	1630

III. 1600–1630

Borgå län								Kymmenegårds län					
Helsingesocknen	Sibbo socknen	Borgå socknen		Perno socknen		Pyttis socknen		Elimä fjärding		Vekkelaks och Vederlaks socknar	Kymmene gård		
		Korpe fjärding	¾	Sävträsksfjärding	¾	Mertelaks fjärding	¾	115 hemman	i övrigt				
1600	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	1600	
1601	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	1601	
1602	327	327	327	327	327	327	327	329	x	329	329	1602	
1603	327	327	x	327	x	327	327	329	x	329	329	1603	
1604	327	327	x	327	x	327	327	329	x	329	329	1604	
1605	327	327	x	327	x	327	327	329	x	x	329	1605	
1606	327	327	x	327	x	327	327	329	x	x	329	1606	
1607	327	327	x	327	x	327	x	329	x	x	329	1607	
1608	327	327	x	327	x	327	x	329	x	x	329	1608	
1609	327	327	x	327	x	327	x	329	x	x	329	1609	
1610	327	327	x	327	x	327	x	329	x	x	329	1610	
1611	327	327	x	327	x	327	x	329	x	x	329	1611	
1612	327	327	x	327	x	327	x	329	x	x	329	1612	
1613	327	327	327	327	x	327	x	329	x	x	329	1613	
1614	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1614	
1615	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1615	
1616	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1616	
1617	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	~	x	x	329	1617	
1618	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1618	
1619	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1619	
1620	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1620	
1621	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1621	
1622	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1622	
1623	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1623	
1624	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1624	
1625	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1625	
1626	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1626	
1627	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1627	
1628	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1628	
1629	327	327	327	327	327	327	x	329	x	x	329	1629	
1630	~	~	~	~	~	~	~	329	x	x	329	1630	

338: see also Karelen (Almquist 1917–1923, III, 128–133)

Layout, terminology, and abbreviations

The records are labelled by type and contextualized by providing the year, bailiwick number, bailiff, bailiwick category, and writing context appropriate for each record. The bailiwick numbers are based on Almquist 1917–1923 (see the bailiwick tables). The provenances of the records are signalled with highlight colours: blue for the central administration, grey for unclear provenance, and no highlighting for locally composed records. At times, individual records have been analysed in detail, while some have been afforded less attention. The provenances have therefore been assigned by a combination of generalizations and specific analyses and should be taken as suggestions.⁶

The layout of the information is as follows:

	Year	Bailiff	Record type	Bailiwick type	Folios per year
Year	1567				1010 fol.
Bailiwick number	327	Jören Jacobsson		District bailiwick	183 fol.
Shelf mark	3287 1-95	Main account			
	3288 1-7	Storage account			
	8-11	Miscellaneous		Lönings register	
	12-26	Receipts			
	3289 1-34	Bailiff's concept			
	35-48	Inventory	s		
	49-62	Miscellaneous		Förtärnings register	
Folios	321	Henrik Henriksson		District bailiwick	517 fol.
	3290 1-130; 144-149	Main account		f. 146-149: tithes	
	131-143	Storage account			
	3291 1-19	Annual taxes			
	3292 1-54	Ecclesiastical rec.			
	3293 1-65	Ecclesiastical rec.			
	66-77	Register on fines			
	78-91	Receipts			
	3294 1-100	Cadastral		f. 90-100: tenants	
	101-120	Register on fines			
	121-125	Tenant farms			
	126-133	Ecclesiastical rec.		Helsinge socken	
	134-139	Ecclesiastical rec.		Sibbo sicken	
	140-154	Ecclesiastical rec.		Borgå socken	
	155-166	Ecclesiastical rec.		Pernå socken	
	167-172	Ecclesiastical rec.		Esbo kapellgåll	
	173-182	Ecclesiastical rec.		Kyrklätt socken	
	183-192	Ecclesiastical rec.		Victis socken	
	193-194	Receipts	s		
	329	Måns Jönsson		District bailiwick	310 fol.
	3295 1-71	Main account			
	72	Receipts	s		

Three codicological abbreviations are used:

- A = Folios in the agenda format⁷
- Qto = Folios in the quarto format
- s = Seal

⁶ The catalogue is rooted in the research found in the present writer's dissertation (Eskola 2020), and for more information on the overall thinking and choices made, see said dissertation generally and, more specifically, the introduction (p. 1 ff.) and "Notes on administrative terminology" (pp. 18–19).

⁷ A format where a sheet of paper is folded twice on the long edge to produce a tall and narrow booklet.

Categories for records

Category:	Contemporary / Swedish term:
Account (unspecified)	Räkenskap
Main account	Huvud räkenskap
Estate account	Huvud räkenskap (gård)
Storage account	Fataburs räkenskap
Parson tax account	Präst ränta räkenskap
Tenant account	Räkenskap för landbor
Additional tax account	Hjälpgård räkenskap
Armoury account	Arkli räkenskap
Arrears account	Rest räkenskap
Bailiff's concept	Koncept räkenskap
Estate concept	Koncept räkenskap (gård)
Income / expense register	Uppbörds / Utgifts register
Registers concerning:	
Annual taxes	Årliga ränta
Parson taxes	Präst ränta
Tenant farms	Landbo ränta
Arrears	Rest
Crop yield	Årsväxt
Inventory	Inventarium
Record on fines	Sacköres register
Receipts	Qvittenser
Armoury register	Arkli register
Mantals register (untransl.)	
Corvée register	Dagsverks register
Salary register	Lönings register
Ödes längd (untransl.)	
Hjonelagh längd (untransl.)	
Cadastre	Jordebook
Ecclesiastical record	Tiende register (or similar payments, e.g., nebbeskatt)
Miscellaneous	

The Catalogue

Nyland			
1540			668 fol.
321	Hans Jönsson	District bailiwick	185 fol.
2918	1-80	Main account	
	81-90	Receipts	
2919	1-75	Annual taxes	
	76-95	Miscellaneous	
338	Nils Månsson Grabbe	District bailiwick	483 fol.
2920	1-483	Cadastre	
1541			429 fol.
321	Hans Jönsson (1.1.1541–30.7.1541)	District bailiwick	33 fol.
2921	1-25	Main account	
	26-33	Receipts	
321	Arvid Olsson Wildeman (30.7.1541–1.1.1542)	District bailiwick	354 fol.
2922	1-80	Income register	
	81-85	Receipts	
	86-99	Expense register	
2923	1-57	Main account	
	58-70	Receipts	
2924	1-141	Cadastre	
2925	1-5	Inventory	30.7.1541
	6-9	Salary register	
	10-13	Corvée register	
	14-17	Miscellaneous	
	18-23	Annual taxes	
2926	1-21	Register on fines	
338	Nils Månsson Grabbe	District bailiwick	42 fol.
2927	1-42	Cadastre	
1542			313 fol.
321	Arvid Olsson Wildeman	District bailiwick	278 fol.
2928	1-72	Income register	
	73-90	Incomes/expenses	
	91-94	Receipts	
2929	1-69	Main account	
	70-72	Miscellaneous	
	73-75	Salary register	
2930	1-109	Cadastre	
327	Knut Matsson Skrivare (3.7.1542–31.12.1542)	Estate bailiwick	35 fol.
2931	1-8	Estate concept	
	9-21	Estate concept	
2932	1-14	Estate account	Begins with an inventory dated 3.7.1542

1543				339 fol.
321	Arvid Olsson Wildeman		District bailiwick	237 fol.
2933	1-41	Main account		
	42-58	Receipts		
2934	1-13	Income and expense reg		
	14-46	Income and expense reg		
2935	1-133	Cadastre		
338	Nils Månsson Grabbe		District bailiwick	102 fol.
2936	1-102	Cadastre	Page instead of folio numbering	
1544				564 fol.
321	Arvid Olsson Wildeman		District bailiwick	387 fol.
2937	1-37	Bailiff's concept		
	38-39	Additional taxes		
	40-51	Miscellaneous	Special register	
	52-55	Receipts		
2938	1-62	Main account		
2939	1-42	Annual taxes		
	43-57	Register on fines		
	58-106	Miscellaneous	Veckekost	
2940	1-164	Cadastre		
327	Knut Matsson Skrivare		Estate bailiwick	72 fol.
2941	1-29	Estate account		
2942	1-34	Estate concept	Landbönder, avel	
	35	Receipts		
	36-39	Miscellaneous		
	40-43	Register on fines	A Landbönder	
338	Nils Månsson Grabbe		District bailiwick	105 fol.
2943	1-105	Cadastre		
1545				386 fol.
321	Arvid Olsson Wildeman			344 fol.
2944	1-26	Main account		
2945	1-38	Main account		
2946	1-46	Bailiff's concept	F. 43-46: summaries by the chamber?	
2947	1-55r	Annual taxes		
	55v-62	Additional taxes		
	63-65	Miscellaneous	Corvées	
	66-84	Register on fines		
2948	1-149	Cadastre		
327	Knut Matsson Skrivare		Estate bailiwick	42 fol.
2949	1-12	Estate account	Incomes	
2950	1-30	Estate account	Expenses	

1546		114 fol.	
321	Arvid Olsson Wildeman	District bailiwick	100 fol.
2951 1-25	Bailiff's concept		Incomes
2952 1-47	Annual taxes		
47v-56	Miscellaneous	Raseborg slott: avel, årsväxt etc.	
57-75	Register on fines		
327	Bertil Håkansson	Estate bailiwick	14 fol.
2953 1-11	Main account		Expenses
12	Main account		Incomes (fragment)
12-14	Miscellaneous		Misplaced folios?
1547		368 fol.	
321	Arvid Olsson Wildeman	District bailiwick	167 fol.
2954 1-38	Bailiff's concept		Expenses etc.
2955 1-39	Main account		Incomes etc.
2956 1-60	Annual taxes		
2957 1-30	Register on fines	f. 29v-30r: Ekenäs stad	
327	Bertil Håkansson	District bailiwick	201 fol.
2958 1-10	Main account		1/2 (incomes)
2959 1-14	Main account		2/2 (expenses)
2960 1-26	Estate concept		
27-29	Receipts		
2961 1-108	Cadastre	Page instead of folio numbering	
109-116	Annual taxes	Länsmans räkningen	
117-148	Register on fines		
1548		264 fol.	
321	Peder Svenske	District bailiwick	103 fol.
2962 1-30	Bailiff's concept		Incomes
31-36	Receipts		
2963 1-57	Annual taxes		
58-60	Additional taxes		
61-67	Inventory	s	12.11.1548
327	Jöns Månsson Skrivare	District bailiwick	106 fol.
2964 1-24	Main account		1/2 (incomes)
25-30	Storage account		
2965 1-18; 20-22	Bailiff's concept		2/2 (expenses)
19	Receipts		
2966 1-12	Bailiff's concept		1/2 (incomes)
13-14	Inventory	s	
15-16	Register on fines		Concerning tenants
2967 1-30	Main account		2/2 (expenses etc.)
2968 1-8	Tenant farms		
Västra pr., Borgå län	Her Karl Folkesson	Prosteri	55 fol.
2969 1-8	Parson tax account		
9-22	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken	
23-31	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken	
32-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken	
52-55	Receipts		

1549		462 fol.
321	Peder Svenske	District bailiwick 272 fol.
2970 1-41	Main account	Incomes & expenses
2971 1-25	Bailiff's concept	Incomes
2972 1-42	Bailiff's concept	Expenses
43-46	Receipts	
2973 1-4	Storage account	1549 (Per Svenske)
5-12	Storage account	1550 (Per Svenske)
13-22	Storage account	1551 (Bengt Joensson Skrivare)
23-28	Storage account	1552 (Bengt Joensson Skrivare)
2974 1-58	Annual taxes	
59-62	Parson taxes	
63-67	Additional taxes	
68-69	Crop yield	Årsväxt
2975 1-63	Ecclesiastical rec.	
327	Jöns Månsson Skrivare	District bailiwick 190 fol.
2976 1-52	Main account	
2977 1-114	Cadastré	
115-129	Annual taxes	
2978 1-9	Estate account	
1550		454 fol.
321	Peder Svenske	District bailiwick 213 fol.
2979 1-16; 26-53	Main account	
17-18	Miscellaneous	Anno 1551
19-25	Receipts	
2980 1-40	Bailiff's concept	Raseborg slott
41-48	Bailiff's concept	Raseborg ladugård
2981 1-12	Estate account	Raseborg ladugård
2982 1-44	Annual taxes	
45-46	Crop yield	
2983 1-54	Ecclesiastical rec.	
327	Erik Jacobsson Spore	District bailiwick 227 fol.
2984 1-60	Main account	
2985 1-17	Bailiff's concept	
18-19	Receipts	
20-39	Bailiff's concept	
40-51	Estate account	
2986 1-12	Annual taxes	Page instead of folio numbering in this signum
13-94	Cadastré	Pp. 169-179: Borgå gårds ränta, avel och landbönder
95-116	Mantals register	
Västra pr., Borgå län	Her Karl Folkesson	Prosteri 6 fol.
2987 1-6	Parson tax account	
Prosteri	Her Henrik (Jacobi)	Prosteri 8 fol.
2988 1-2	Parson tax account	
3-8	Ecclesiastical rec.	Anno 1547 - 1549

1551		548 fol.
321	Bengt Joensson Skrivare	District bailiwick 248 fol.
2989 1-74	Main account	
2990 1-39	Bailiff's concept	
40-54	Bailiff's concept	Raseborg ladugård
55-62	Receipts	
2991 1-13	Estate account	Raseborg ladugård
2992 1-50	Ecclesiastical rec.	
2992a 1-49	Register on fines	F. 38-49: Prost ting
327	Erik Jacobsson Spore	District bailiwick 149 fol.
2993 1-63	Main account	
2994 1-32	Bailiff's concept	Expenses
33-38	Receipts	
39-68	Register on fines	
2995 1-9	Storage account	Helsingefors
2996 1-9	Estate account	Borgå gård
321	Bengt Joensson Skrivare	District bailiwick 55 fol.
2997 1-54	Annual taxes	F. 1-2: Helsinge socken (bailiwick 327?)
55	Crop yield	
327	Erik Jacobsson Spore	District bailiwick 86 fol.
2998 1-11	Annual taxes	Page instead of folio numbering
12-80	Cadastre	
81-86	Tenant farms	
Prosteri	Her Henrik (Jacobi)	Prosteri 10 fol.
2999 1-6	Parson tax account	
7-8	Miscellaneous	Notes. Seal?
9-10	Receipts	
1552		402 fol.
321	Bengt Joensson Skrivare	District bailiwick 268 fol.
3000 1-55	Main account	
56-60	Inventory	3.3.1553
3001 1-8	Estate account	
3002 1-55	Annual taxes	
56-111	Ecclesiastical rec.	
112-153	Register on fines	F. 138-153: Prost ting
3003 1-5	Parson tax account	
6-12	Ecclesiastical rec.	Tenala socken
13-24	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pojo socken
25-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo socken
34-39	Ecclesiastical rec.	Siundo socken
40-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	Ingo socken

327	Erik Jacobsson Spore	District bailiwick	101 fol.
3004	1-39; 46-49	Main account	
	40-45	Inventory	Borgå och Helsingfors
3005	1-17	Estate account	Incomes. Helsingfors
3006	1-7	Estate account	Incomes and expenses. Borgå ladugård
3007	1-3	Miscellaneous	Debts
	4-7	Receipts	
	8-13	Inventory	Concerning Borgå & Helsingfors; 12.10.1552
	14-19	Storage account	
	20-28	Storage account	
3008	Missing. According to Grönblad's catalogue: "Aff Perno (och Sibbo) soken nebbeskats Register pro anno 1552. Synes vara ett fragment".		
Prosteri	Her Anders, prost, Borgå län	Prosteri	33 fol.
3009	1-6	Register on fines	A Inc. prost ting
	7-12	Parson tax account	f. 12v: receipt
	13-23	Ecclesiastical rec.	Tiende; Pyttis socken
	24-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt; Pyttis socken
1553			692 fol.
321	Erik Jacobsson Spore	District bailiwick	101 fol.
3010	1-70	Main account	
3011	1-23	Bailiff's concept	Incomes
3012	1-6	Storage account	
	7-8	Armoury account	
321	Bengt Joensson Skrivare, Michaelis 1552 – 3.3.1553	District bailiwick	41 fol.
3013	1-21	Main account	Michaelis 1552 – 3.3.1553
	22-33; 36-41	Bailiff's concept	
	34-35	Receipts	
321	Erik Spore / Bengt Skrivare	District bailiwick	254 fol.
3014	1-54	Annual taxes	
3015	1-63	Cadastre	Helsinge, Sibbo (Borgå län); Victis, Loppis (Tavashus län)
	64-67	Receipts	
	68-70	Miscellaneous	
3016	1-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt register
3017	1-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt register
	57-60	Miscellaneous	
327	Nils Persson	District bailiwick	233 fol.
3018	1-32	Main account	
3019	1-6	Storage account	
	7-12	Storage account	
3020	1-6	Estate account	
	7-12	Estate account	
	13-16	Miscellaneous	Misplaced. Anno 1549
3021	1-14	Annual taxes	Page not folio numbering in the record. Anno 1552
	15-110	Cadastre	Anno 1552
	111-119	Tenant farms	Anno 1552
3022	1-20	Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt register: Perno och Sibbo; Anno 1552
	21-38	Annual taxes	
	39-46	Cadastre	Borgå socken
	47-54	Tenant farms	
321	Erik Spore / Bengt Skrivare	District bailiwick	63 fol.
3022a	1-63	Register on fines	Inc. prost ting

1554		357 fol.	
321	Hans Larsson Skalm	District bailiwick	227 fol.
3023	1-44 Main account		1/2
3024	1-47 Main account		2/2
3025	1-6 Inventory	25.11.1553 Raseborg	
	7-11 Inventory	11.11.1553 Helsingfors	
3026	1-44 Annual taxes		
	45-50 Receipts		
3027	1-75 Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt register	
327	Nils Persson	District bailiwick	130 fol.
3028	1-54; 61-63 Main account		
	55-60 Storage account		
3029	1-26 Bailiff's concept	Opbörd/Utgift	
	27-30 Miscellaneous A	Skatte smör	
	31-35 Miscellaneous	Utspisningen	
	36-40 Bailiff's concept	Borgå ladugård	
	41-44 Storage account		
3030	1-18 Annual taxes		
	19-23 Receipts		
1555		478 fol.	
321	Hans Larsson Skalm	District bailiwick	131 fol.
3031	1-47 Main account		1/2
3032	1-36 Main account		2/2
3033	1-9 Annual taxes		
	10-48 Annual taxes		
327	Nils Persson	District bailiwick	340 fol.
3034	1-68 Main account		
3035	1-8 Storage account		
	9-16 Bailiff's concept	Borgå gård	
	17-35 Bailiff's concept	Expenses, Borgå län	
	36-39 Storage account		
	40-47 Receipts		
	48-52 Mantals register		
3036	1-3 Receipts	(Borgå län)	
	4-14 Additional tax account	Borgå, Perno & Pyttis socknar (Borgå län)	
	15-26 Additional tax account	Hollola, Nyby & Elimä socknar (Tavastehus län)	
	27-32 Receipts	(Tavastehus län)	
3037	1-14 Annual taxes		
	15-28 Bailiff's concept	Incomes	
	29-32 Inventory s	1.10.1555	
3038	1-2 Miscellaneous	Fragment	
	3-76 Cadastre	Landbönder: f. 47-48; 69-76	
3039	1-11 Ecclesiastical rec.	Tionde, Pyttis socken	
	12-23 Ecclesiastical rec.	Tionde, Perno socken	
	24-36 Ecclesiastical rec.	Tionde, Borgå socken	
	37-43 Ecclesiastical rec.	Tionde, Sibbo socken	
	44-55 Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt smör, Pyttis socken	
	56-67 Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt smör, Perno	
	68-80 Ecclesiastical rec.	Näbbskatt smör, Borgå	
Prosteri	Her Anders, prost, Borgå län	Prosteri	7 fol.
3039a	1-7 Parson tax account		

1556		1056 fol.
328	Anders Korp	District bailiwick 399 fol.
3040	1-66 Main account	1/2
3041	1-58 Main account	2/2
3042	1-32 Storage account	
3043	1-4 Armoury account	
3044	1-30 Annual taxes	
	31-76 Cadastre	
3045	1-19 Ecclesiastical rec.	
	20 Receipts s	
3046	1-2 Additional tax account	
	3-26 Additional taxes	
	27-40 Register on fines	
3047	1-38 Receipts	
3048	1-2 Miscellaneous A	
	3-15 Inventory	1.12.1555, Helsingefors gård
	16-30 Inventory s	Five seals on f. 29.
	31-39 Inventory	4.1.1556, Raseborg
	40-65 Ecclesiastical rec.	
324	Anders Larsson	District bailiwick 88 fol.
3049	1-30 Main account	
3050	1-20 Bailiff's concept	
	21-52 Ecclesiastical rec.	
	53-58 Miscellaneous	
323	Lydick Pålsson	District bailiwick 110 fol.
3051	1-27; 31-35 Main account	
	28-30 Additional tax account	
3052	1-2 Miscellaneous	
	3-17 Annual taxes	
	18-26 Register on fines	
	27-30 Receipts	
	31-34 Additional taxes	
	35-37 Miscellaneous	
3053	1-12 Bailiff's concept	
	13-38 Ecclesiastical rec.	
321	Henrik Schultz [called Tysk]	District bailiwick 153 fol.
3054	1-28 Main account	1/2
	29 Receipts	
3055	1-26 Main account	2/2
3056	1-25 Bailiff's concept	
	26-29 Receipts	
3057	1-8 Storage account	
	9-11 Storage account	
3058	1-13 Annual taxes	
	14-29 Register on fines	F. 26-29: proest ting
	30-58 Ecclesiastical rec.	

Raseborgs län		Hans Antonii (Tönnesson)	Prosteri	22 fol.
3059	1-8	Parson tax account		
3060	1-10	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	11-14	Receipts		
327		Mats Sigfridsson	District bailiwick	197 fol.
3061	1-34	Bailiff's concept		
	35-38	Receipts		
3062	1-32	Main account		1/2
3063	1-32	Main account		2/2
	33-38	Inventory	s	Seals on f. 38.
3064	1-6	Storage account		
3065	1-12	Additional tax account		
3066	1-12	Annual taxes		
	13-41	Cadastre		
	42-49	Tenant farms		
	50-55	Register on fines		
3067	1-12	Additional taxes		
	13-16	Receipts		
Borgå län		Andreas Laurentii(?)	Prosteri	9 fol.
3068	1-9	Parson tax account		
329		Olof Jacobsson	District bailiwick	78 fol.
3069	1-26	Main account		
	27-28	Miscellaneous		
	29-34	Additional tax account		
	35-40	Annual taxes		
	41-58	Cadastre		
	59-72	Bailiff's concept		
	73-78	Receipts		
1557				1243 fol.
328		Anders Korp	District bailiwick	119 fol.
3070	1-93	Main account		
	85	Receipts	s	
3071	1-6	Armoury account		
3072	1-16	Annual taxes		
	17-20	Additional taxes		
324		Anders Larsson	District bailiwick	97 fol.
3073	1-43	Bailiff's concept		
	44-47	Receipts		
	48-49	Storage account		
3074	1-44	Main account		2/2 (see 3082)
	45-48	Additional tax account		
325		Peder Mandel	Estate bailiwick	6 fol.
3075	1-6	Estate account		

324	Anders Larsson	District bailiwick	83 fol.
3076	1-3	Tenant farms	
	4-17	Annual taxes	
	18-20	Additional taxes	
	21-34	Register on fines	
	35-39	Additional taxes	
3077	1-8	Parson tax account	
	9-12	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	13-44	Ecclesiastical rec.	
323	Lydeke Påvelsson	District bailiwick	157 fol.
3078	1-58	Main account	
	59-62	Storage account	
	63-70	Inventory	
3079	1-36	Bailiff's concept	
	37-39	Receipts	
	40-46	Annual taxes	
3080	1-20	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	21-41	Ecclesiastical rec.	
321	Henrik Schultz [called Tysk]	District bailiwick	84 fol.
3081	1-81	Main account	
	82-84	Additional tax account	
324	Anders Larsson	District bailiwick	38 fol.
3082	1-38	Main account	1/2 (see 3074)
321	Henrik Schultz [called Tysk]	District bailiwick	124 fol.
3083	1-30	Bailiff's concept	
3084	1-6	Parson tax account	
3085	1-10	Storage account	
3086	1-12	Annual taxes	
	13-17	Additional taxes	
	18-19	Tenant farms	
	20-26	Register on fines	
	27-29r	Register on fines	
	29v-33	Receipts	
3087	1-18	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	19-45	Ecclesiastical rec.	
327	Kristoffer Jörensso 7.3.1557-	District bailiwick	108 fol.
3088	1-66	Main account	
	67-96	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	97-102	Miscellaneous	
	103-108	Inventory	Seals f. 108
327	Mats Sigfridsson 30.9.1556-7.3.1557	District bailiwick	92 fol.
3089	1-2	Miscellaneous	
	3-9	Tenant farms	
	10-43	Main account	
3090	1-20	Bailiff's concept	
	21-26	Storage account	
	27-34	Additional tax account	
	35-39	Inventory	
3091	1-6	Miscellaneous	
	7-10	Receipts	

327	Kristoffer Jörensso 7.3.1557–	District bailiwick	223 fol.
3092	1-138	Cadastre	
	139-147	Annual taxes	
	148-155	Register on fines	
	156-195	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	196-223	Mantals register	
329	Olof Jacobsson	District bailiwick	112 fol.
3093	1-5	Register on fines	A
	6-70; 79	Main account	
	71-74	Additional tax account	
	75-78	Storage account	
3094	1-23	Cadastre	
	24-33	Annual taxes	
1558			1520 fol.
328	Anders Korp	District bailiwick	304 fol.
3095	1-116	Main account	
3096	1-20	Bailiff's concept	
3097	1-8	Bailiff's concept	
	9-26	Receipts	
3098	1-29	Storage account	
	30-45	Armoury account	
3099	1-20	Miscellaneous	A
3100	1-11	Annual taxes	Includes other taxes and incomes as well
	12-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3101	1-10	Register on fines	
	11-14	Miscellaneous	Årsväxt/fisk
	15-16	Miscellaneous	"Skiptzfracte Peninger"
	17-22	Miscellaneous	Lön register
3102	1-22	Ecclesiastical rec.	
325	Peder Mandel: 1.10.1557 – till anno 1558	Estate bailiwick	6 fol.
3103	1-6	Estate account	
321 (Esbo gård)	Joen Nilsson Skrivare: 30.5.1558 – Michaelis 1558	Estate bailiwick	4 fol.
3104	1-4	Estate account	
325	Peder Mandel: 1.10.1557 – till anno 1558	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
3105	1-8	Bailiff's concept	A
324	Anders Larsson: Michaelis 1557 – 29.5.1558	District bailiwick	125 fol.
3106	1-41	Main account	
	42-43	Additional tax account	
3107	1-20	Bailiff's concept	
3108	1-4	Storage account	
	5-8	Storage account	A
3109	1-6	Parson tax account	
3110	1-5	Register on fines	A
	6-8	Miscellaneous	A
3111	1-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	34	Receipts	
	35-40	Ecclesiastical rec.	

323	Lydeke Påvelsson: 29.9.1557–19.2.1558?	District bailiwick	56 fol.
3112	1-4	Register on fines	
	5-29	Bailiff's concept	
	30-32	Receipts	
	33-44	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3113	1-4	Storage account	
3114	1-4	Parson tax account	Anders Smålänning
	5-8	Parson tax account	Lydeke Påvelsson
323	Anders Arvidsson Smålänning: 19.2.1558 – Michaelis 1558	District bailiwick	137 fol.
3115	1-8	Inventory	s 3.10.1558
	9-61; 69-75	Main account	
	62-68	Storage account	
3116	1-2	Additional tax account	
3117	1-39	Bailiff's concept	
	40-42	Receipts	
	43-52	Mantals register	
3118	1-8	Register on fines	
326	Påvel Hansson: 20.3.1558 – Michaelis 1558	Estate bailiwick	21 fol.
3119	1-14	Bailiff's concept	
3120	1-4	Estate account	
	5-7	Additional taxes	Bailiwick nr. 321?
321	Henrik Schultz [called Tysk]: Michaelis 1557 – 8.4.1558	District bailiwick	71 fol.
3121	1-17	Main account	1/2
3122	1-24	Main account	2/2
3123	1-4	Mantals register	
	5; 8-20	Bailiff's concept	
	6-7	Miscellaneous	A
	21-24	Register on fines	
	25-30	Receipts	
321	Joen Nilsson Skrivare: 8.4.1558 – Michaelis 1558	District bailiwick	354 fol.
3124	1-40	Main account	1/2
	41-42	Parson tax account	
	43-45	Additional tax account	
3125	1-26	Bailiff's concept	
3126	1-28; 32-41	Main account	2/2
	29-31	Parson tax account	
	42	Receipts	
3127	1-11	Mantals register	A
	12-54	Miscellaneous	
3128	1-11	Storage account	
3129	1-33	Annual taxes	Similar to 3130
3130	1-26	Annual taxes	Similar to 3129
3131	1-10	Annual taxes	
	11-12	Additional taxes	
	13-14	Tenant farms	
3132	1-34	Ecclesiastical rec.	Qto Small folios 21–33
3133	1-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3134	1-9	Register on fines	
	10	Receipts	s

327	Kristoffer Jörensson	District bailiwick	285 fol.
3135	1-99	Main account	
	100-105	Storage account	
3136	1-25	Bailiff's concept	
	26-28	Receipts	
3137	1-8	Annual taxes	
3138	1-40	Cadastre	
	41-63	Cadastre	Ecclesiastical record?
	64-110	Miscellaneous	Förtärnings register
	111-137	Mantals register	
	138-144	Register on fines	
329	Olof Jacobsson	District bailiwick	149 fol.
3139	1-67; 73-74	Main account	
	68-72	Additional tax account	
3140	1-5	Storage account	
3141	1-10	Register on fines	A
	11-28	Annual taxes	
	29-50	Cadastre	
3142	1-20	Ecclesiastical rec.	
1559			1435 fol.
328	Anders Korp	District bailiwick	426 fol.
3143	1-126	Main account	Folios of KA 3143–51 are damaged and fragmentary
	127-132	Additional tax account	
3144	1-77	Bailiff's concept	
3145	1-58	Mantals register	A
3146	1-21	Additional taxes	
3147	1-46	Cadastre	
3148	1-21	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3149	1-18	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	19-35	Miscellaneous	A
3150	1-11	Register on fines	
3151	1-12	Miscellaneous	
	13-25	Receipts	
323	Anders Arvidsson Smålänning	District bailiwick	209 fol.
3152	1-36	Main account	1/2
3153	1-40	Main account	2/2
3154	1-5	Parson tax account	
	6-8	Additional tax account	
	9-36	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3155	1-8	Storage account	
	9-14	Storage account	
3156	1-23	Bailiff's concept	
3157	1-16	Annual taxes	
	17-18	Additional taxes	
	19-30	Register on fines	
3158	1-7; 30	Inventory	Fol. 30 is the first folio
	8-29	Cadastre	

321	Joen Nilsson Skrivare	District bailiwick	161 fol.
3159	1-80	Main account	
	81	Receipts	
3160	1-17; 21-39	Bailiff's concept	
	18-20	Miscellaneous	A
	40	Miscellaneous	
	41-42	Receipts	
3161	1-8	Inventory	s Ekenäs 5.10.1559
	9-13	Inventory	
	14-18	Additional tax account	
3162	1-16	Storage account	
3163	1-4	Parson tax account	
322	Tönnnes Mikaelsson	Estate bailiwick	6 fol.
3164	1-6	Estate account	Raseborg
325	Truls Persson	Estate bailiwick	7 fol.
	7-13	Estate account	Esbo
326?	Mats Olsson	Estate bailiwick	7 fol.
	14-20	Estate account	Pojo
321	Joen Nilsson Skrivare	District bailiwick	215 fol.
3165	1-34	Annual taxes	
3166	1-62	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	33r, 37v, 62r	Receipts	
3167	1-66	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3168	1-25	Additional taxes	A
	26-31	Miscellaneous	A
3169	1-22	Register on fines	
327	Kristoffer Jörensso	District bailiwick	247 fol.
3170	1-104	Main account	
	105-111	Storage account	
3171	1-29	Bailiff's concept	
	30-31	Receipts	
	32-41	Annual taxes	
3172	1-80	Cadastre	
	81-89	Register on fines	
	90-95	Inventory	s Seals on f. 94
329	Kristoffer Jörensso	District bailiwick	157 fol.
3173	1-91	Main account	
	92-96	Storage account	
	97-99	Inventory	s Fall 1559. Seals on f. 99
	100-101	Inventory	s Fall 1558. Seals on f. 101
3174	1-19	Bailiff's concept	
	20-46	Miscellaneous	Förtärnings register
	47-53	Mantals register	
	54-56	Receipts	

1560		881 fol.	
328	Erik Svensson	District bailiwick	67 fol.
3175	1-14	Main account	
	15-36	Inventory	s Seals on f. 15 (and 34?)
	37-67	Main account	Folios 37, 38 and 66 missing?
321	Joen Nilsson Skrivare / Jacob Månsson	District bailiwick	109 fol.
3176	1; 19-22	Receipts	s Five original receipts
	2-18; 23-54	Main account	Joen Nilsson
3177	1-30	Main account	Jacob Månsson
3178	1-13	Bailiff's concept	Jacob Månsson
3179	1-6	Storage account	Joen Nilsson
3180	1-6	Parson tax account	Joen Nilsson
325	Truls Persson	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
3181	1-8	Estate account	Esbo
322	Tønnes Mikaelsson	Estate bailiwick	6 fol.
	9-14	Estate account	Raseborg
326	Mats Persson	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
	15-22	Estate account	Pojo (fol. 22 all three estates)
321	Joen Nilsson Skrivare / Jacob Månsson	District bailiwick	91 fol.
	23-40	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3182	1-37	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	38-41	Parson taxes	
3183	1-19	Register on fines	
	20-32	Inventory	s 28.6.1560
323	Anders Arvidsson Smålaning	District bailiwick	200 fol.
3184	1-70	Main account	
3185	1-34	Main account	
3186	1-14	Storage account	
3187	1-6	Parson tax account	
3188	1-22	Annual taxes	
3189	1-25; 29-34	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	26-28	Parson taxes	
3189a	1-20	Register on fines	
327	Lars Eriksson	District bailiwick	225 fol.
3190	1-82	Main account	
	83-89	Storage account	
3191	1-39	Additional taxes	s Silver tax register. Seal cut out (f. 38)
3192	1-11	Annual taxes	
	12-76	Cadastre	
	77-89	Register on fines	
	90-97	Miscellaneous	A

329	Erik Olsson	District bailiwick	167 fol.
3193	1-82	Main account	
	83-84	Additional tax account	
	85-92	Storage account	
	93-96	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
3194	1-17	Additional taxes	Seal f. 17
3195	1-11	Annual taxes	
	12-30r	Cadastre	
	30v-45	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	46-49	Register on fines	
	50-54	Receipts	
1561			968 fol.
328	Erik Svensson	District bailiwick	110 fol.
3196	1-62	Main account	
3197	1-3; 10-20	Bailiff's concept	
	4-9	Annual taxes	
	21-26	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	27-48	Receipts	
323	Anders Arvidsson Smålänning	District bailiwick	170 fol.
3198	1-2	Additional tax account	
	3-49	Main account	
3199	1-36	Bailiff's concept	
3200	1-9	Storage account	
3201	1-17	Additional taxes	
3202	1-15	Annual taxes	
3203	1-14	Annual taxes	
3204	1-24	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	25-30	Parson tax account	
321	Jacob Månsson	District bailiwick	119 fol.
3205	1	Additional tax account	
	2-72	Main account	
3206	1-47	Bailiff's concept	
322, 325, 326	Truls Persson, Tønnes Mikaelsson, Mats Persson	Estate bailiwick	45 fol.
3207	1-9	Estate account	Truls Persson, Esbo
	10-20	Estate account	Tønnes Mikaelsson, Raseborg
	21-29	Estate account	Mats Persson, Pojo
	30-34	Inventory	Ekenäs
	35-37	Inventory	Esbo
	38	Inventory	Pojo
	39-44	Inventory	Nye Raseborg. Fatabur
	45	Receipts	
321	Jacob Månsson	District bailiwick	155 fol.
3208	1-26	Annual taxes	
	27-31	Tenant farms	
	32-37	Additional tax account	
3209	1-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3210	1-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	

327	Lars Eriksson	District bailiwick	168 fol.
3211	1-97	Main account	
	98	Additional tax account	
	99-105	Storage account	
	106-107	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
3212	1-40	Cadastre	
	41-50	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	51-56	Register on fines	
	57-61	Receipts	
329	Erik Olsson	District bailiwick	201 fol.
3213	1-2	Receipts	
	3-94; 106-108	Main account	
	95-97	Additional tax account	
	98-105	Storage account	
3214	1-13	Annual taxes	
	14-35	Cadastre	
	36-46	Register on fines	
	47-67	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	68-83	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3215	1-10	Tenant farms	
1562			451 fol.
321	Mikael Östgöte	District bailiwick	85 fol.
3216	1-75	Main account	
	76-85	Inventory	Fatabur
322	Tönnas Mikaelsson	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
3217	1-8	Estate account	Gamle Raseborg
326	Mats Persson	Estate bailiwick	7 fol.
	9-15	Estate account	Pojo
325	Truls Persson	Estate bailiwick	9 fol.
	16-24	Estate account	Esbo
323?	Tomas Olsson: 9.3.1562 – Michaelis 1562	Estate bailiwick	12 fol.
	25-36	Estate account	Laxpojo
322	Tönnas Mikaelsson	Estate bailiwick	5 fol.
3218	1-5	Bailiff's concept	Gamle Raseborg
326	Mats Persson	Estate bailiwick	5 fol.
	6-10	Bailiff's concept	Pojo
325	Truls Persson	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
	11-18	Bailiff's concept	Esbo
323	Tomas Olsson	Estate bailiwick	9 fol.
	19-27	Bailiff's concept	Laxpojo
321	Mikael Östgöte	District bailiwick	187 fol.
	28-37	Bailiff's concept	
3219	1-27	Annual taxes	
3220	1-95	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3221	1-55	Ecclesiastical rec.	
323	Anders Arvidsson Smålänning	District bailiwick	90 fol.
3222	1-45	Main account	
3223	1-23	Bailiff's concept	
3224	1-4	Storage account	
	5-10	Inventory	
3225	1-12	Cadastre	

329	Jöns Månsson & Mårthen Knutson	Estate bailiwick?	26 fol.
3226	1-20	Estate account	
	21-26	Storage account	
1563			910 fol.
327	Henrik Simonsson	District bailiwick	284 fol.
3227	1-94	Main account	
3228	1-67	Mantals register	Inc. fol. 66a and 66b (in agenda format)
3229	1-12	Annual taxes	
	13-14	Miscellaneous	A
	15-16	Miscellaneous	
	17-57	Bailiff's concept	
3230	1-44	Cadastre	
	45-49	Tenant farms	
3231	1-17	Register on fines	
321	Mikael Östgöte	District bailiwick	131 fol.
3232	1-77	Main account	
	78-82	Parson tax account	
	83-92	Additional tax account	
	93-98	Main account	
	99-117	Miscellaneous	Förtärnings register
	118-119	Main account	
3233	1-12	Storage account	
325	Truls Persson	Estate bailiwick	9 fol.
3234	1-9	Estate account	Esbo gård
322	Tönnas Mikaelsson	Estate bailiwick	6 fol.
	10-15	Estate account	Gamle Raseborg gård
326	Mats Persson	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
	16-23	Estate account	Pojo gård
323	Tomas Olsson	Estate bailiwick	10 fol.
	24-33	Estate account	Laxpojo gård
321	Mikael Östgöte	District bailiwick	207 fol.
3235	1-32	Annual taxes	Fol. 29-32: "Bågarna aff Vigtis sochnn"
3236	1-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3237	1-63	Ecclesiastical rec.	Raseborg län
3238	1-29	Register on fines	f. 27v: Ekenäs stad
3239	1-4	Tenant farms	
	5-8	Tenant farms	
	9-13	Tenant farms	Anno 1562
329	Mårthen Knutson	District bailiwick	255 fol.
3240	1-95	Main account	
3241	1-25	Annual taxes	
	26-27	Additional taxes	
	28-69	Cadastre	
	70-99	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	100-109	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pyttis and Eleme socken
	110-127	Register on fines	
	128-134	Receipts	
3242	1-6	Storage account	
3243	1-13	Tenant account	
	14-15	Inventory	
	16-20	Miscellaneous	

1564				996 fol.
327	Henrik Simonsson		District bailiwick	279 fol.
3244	1-96	Main account		
3245	1-9	Storage account		Helsingfors, Borgå och Esbo gårdar
	10-13	Miscellaneous		Lönings register
	14-20	Receipts		
3246	1-45	Cadastre		
	46-54	Annual taxes		
	55-58	Tenant farms		
	59-98	Ecclesiastical rec.		
3247	1-4	Parson tax account		
	5-14	Ecclesiastical rec.		Helsinge socken
	15-22	Ecclesiastical rec.		Sibbo socken
	23-35	Ecclesiastical rec.		Borgå socken
	36-45	Ecclesiastical rec.		Pernå socken
	46-52	Ecclesiastical rec.		Esbo kapellgåll
	53-58	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Kyrkslätt socken
	59-65	Ecclesiastical rec.		Victis socken
321	Olof Jacobsson		District bailiwick	185 fol.
3248	1-4	Miscellaneous		
	5-8	Miscellaneous		
	9-116	Main account		
3249	1-11	Storage account		Ekenäs gård
3250	1-54	Mantals register	A	Ekenäs gård
326	Mats Persson		Estate bailiwick	15 fol.
3251	1-15	Estate account		Pojo gård
322	Tönnes Mikaelsson		Estate bailiwick	13 fol.
	16-28	Estate account		Gamle Raseborg gård
326	Mats Persson		Estate bailiwick	11 fol.
3252	1-11	Estate account		Pojo gård
322	Tönnes Mikaelsson		Estate bailiwick	11 fol.
	12-22	Estate account		Gamle Raseborg gård
321	Olof Jacobsson		District bailiwick	142 fol.
3253	1-12	Annual taxes		
	13-15	Tenant farms		
	16-21	Inventory		Ekenäs gård
	22	Inventory		Gamle Raseborg ladugård
	23-24	Inventory		Pojo ladugård
3254	1-45	Ecclesiastical rec.		Raseborg län
	46-58	Receipts		
3255	1-44	Ecclesiastical rec.		Raseborg län
3256	1-16	Register on fines		

329	Mårthen Knutson	District bailiwick	340 fol.
3257	1-14	Miscellaneous	
	15-93; 98-104;	Main account	
	94-97	Mantals register	Kymmenegård
	105-114	Storage account	
3258	1-30	Annual taxes	f. 14-16: parson taxes, tenant rents
	31-86	Bailiff's concept	
	87-108	Cadastre	
	109-130	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	131-150	Register on fines	
	151-159	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	160-165	Receipts	
	166-167	Miscellaneous	Lönings register. Kymmenegård
3259	1-14	Tenant farms	
3260	1-42	Miscellaneous	
1565			976 fol.
327	Henrik Simonsson	District bailiwick	286 fol.
3261	1-97	Main account	86v-89: parson taxes; 90-91: kostgården
3262	1-9	Storage account	
	10-16	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	17-37	Register on fines	
	38-40	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	41-46	Receipts	
3263	1-45	Cadastre	
	46-80	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	81-86	Tenant farms	
3264	1-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	
321	Olof Jacobsson	District bailiwick	141 fol.
3265	1-8	Miscellaneous	f. 3: receipt
	9-116	Main account	
	117-119	Parson taxes	
3266	1-11	Storage account	Ekenäs gård
3267	1-11	Storage account	Ekenäs gård
322	Tönnes Mikaelsson	Estate bailiwick	7 fol.
	12-18	Estate account	Gamle Raseborg gård
326	Mats Pedersson	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
	19-26	Estate account	Pojo gård
321	Olof Jacobsson	District bailiwick	51 fol.
	3268	1-51	Mantals register
322	Tönnes Mikaelsson	Estate bailiwick	9 fol.
	3269	1-9	Estate account
			Gamle Raseborg gård
326	Mats Pedersson	Estate bailiwick	8 fol.
	10-17	Estate account	Pojo gård
	3270	Presumably originally misplaced. Now follows KA 3374 as 3270a. A cadastre of Raseborg for 1577.	
321	Olof Jacobsson	District bailiwick	120 fol.
	3271	1-49	Ecclesiastical rec.
	3272	1-54	Ecclesiastical rec.
	3273	1-17	Register on fines

329	Morten Knutsson	District bailiwick	346 fol.
3274	1-122	Main account	
	123-130	Storage account	Kymmene gård
	131-135	Additional tax account	Kostgård
3275	1-32	Annual taxes	
	33-37	Miscellaneous	
	38-39	Receipts	s
	40-91	Bailiff's concept	
	92-101; 104-13	Receipts	s
	102-103	Salary register	Lönings register
3276	1-23	Cadastre	
	24-39	Tenant farms	
	40-79	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	80-98	Register on fines	
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1566			916 fol.
<hr/>			
327	Jören Jacobsson	District bailiwick	352 fol.
3277	1-5; 13-124	Main account	
	6-12	Storage account	
	125-130	Miscellaneous	Lönings register?
3278	1-64	Cadastre	f. 1-5: förökt/förminskat
	65-124	Ecclesiastical rec.	f. 65-68: undervisning
	125-135	Ecclesiastical rec.	Tenala socken
	136-141	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	142-153	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	154-164	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	165-169	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll
	170-180	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Kyrkslätt socken
	181-192	Ecclesiastical rec.	Qto Victis socken
	193-206	Register on fines	
	207-222	Receipts	
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321	Henrik Henriksson	District bailiwick	295 fol.
3279	1-2	Receipts	s
	3-138	Main account	f. 3-12: miscellaneous; f. 135-138: on tithes
3280	1-10	Inventory	s Ekenäs gård
	11-20	Storage account	Ekenäs gård
	21-30	Register on fines	
3281	1-42	Mantals register	A Dozens (?) of empty folios after f. 42
3282	1-17	Annual taxes	
3283	1-50	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3284	1-18	Receipts	
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329	Måns Jönsson	District bailiwick	269 fol.
3285	1-110	Main account	
	111-120	Storage account	
	121-122	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
3286	1-59	Cadastre	f.47-59: tenants
	60-109	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	110-127	Register on fines	
	128-147	Receipts	

1567		1010 fol.	
327	Jören Jacobsson	District bailiwick	183 fol.
3287	1-95	Main account	
3288	1-7	Storage account	
	8-11	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	12-26	Receipts	
3289	1-34	Bailiff's concept	
	35-48	Inventory	s
	49-62	Miscellaneous	Förtärnings register
321	Henrik Henriksson	District bailiwick	517 fol.
3290	1-130; 144-149	Main account	f. 146-149: tithes
	131-143	Storage account	
3291	1-19	Annual taxes	
3292	1-54	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3293	1-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	66-77	Register on fines	
	78-91	Receipts	
3294	1-100	Cadastre	f. 90-100: tenants
	101-120	Register on fines	
	121-125	Tenant farms	
	126-133	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	134-139	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	140-154	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	155-166	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	167-172	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgåll
	173-182	Ecclesiastical rec.	Kyrkslätt socken
	183-192	Ecclesiastical rec.	Victis socken
	193-194	Receipts	s
329	Måns Jönsson	District bailiwick	310 fol.
3295	1-71	Main account	
	72	Receipts	s
3296	1-7	Storage account	
	8-12	Inventory	Smaller folios
3297	1-53	Bailiff's concept	
3298	1-44	Annual taxes	
3299	1-50	Cadastre	f. 42-50: tenants
	51-63	Register on fines	
	64-77	Receipts	
	78-83	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
3300	1-46	Ecclesiastical rec.	Seals?
1568		447 fol.	
327	Jören Jacobsson	District bailiwick	178 fol.
3301	1-71; 78-116	Main account	f. 107-110: tienden
	72-77	Storage account	
3302	1-14	Receipts	
	15-20	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	21-37	Register on fines	F. 21-25 empty
	38	Miscellaneous	
	39-52	Inventory	s till anno 1568
	53-62	Inventory	s till anno 1569
321	Henrik Henriksson	District bailiwick	55 fol.
3303	1-55	Mantals register	A Ekenäs gård

329	Måns Jönsson	District bailiwick	214 fol.
3304	1-92; 99-108	Main account	f. 1-8: smaller folios
	93-98	Inventory	s Smaller folios
3305	1-8	Storage account	Qto
	9-11	Miscellaneous	Qto Lönings register
3306	1-20	Cadastre	
	21-32	Tenant farms	
	33-40	Receipts	
	41-50	Register on fines	
	51	Receipts	s
3307	1-44	Ecclesiastical rec.	
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1569			488 fol.
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327	Jören Jacobsson	District bailiwick	233 fol.
3308	1-119	Cadastre	
	120-123	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	124-131	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	132-143	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	144-153	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	154-159	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll
	160-171	Ecclesiastical rec.	Kyrkslätt socken
	172-177	Storage account	
	178-186	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	187-193	Receipts	
	194-210	Register on fines	
	211-231	Miscellaneous	Avkortningen 1572?
	232-233	Miscellaneous	
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321	Henrik Henriksson	District bailiwick	255 fol.
3309	1-91	Main account	
	92-98	Storage account	
3310	1-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	54-64	Register on fines	
	65-68	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
3311	1-60	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3312	1-18	Annual taxes	
	19-29	Receipts	
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1570			596 fol.
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327	Jören Jacobsson	District bailiwick	198 fol.
3313	1-78	Main account	
3314	1-6	Storage account	
	7-14	Miscellaneous	s Lönings register; 1569, 1570
	15-18	Miscellaneous	Lönings register 1570
	19-24	Receipts	
3315	1-24	Cadastre	
	25-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	34-45	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	46-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	52-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	60-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll
	66-75	Ecclesiastical rec.	Anno 1570–1571, Kyrkslätt socken
	76-83	Ecclesiastical rec.	Victis socken
	84-95	Register on fines	
	96	Receipts	

321	Henrik Henriksson	District bailiwick	398 fol.
3316	1-118	Main account	
	119-126	Storage account	Ekenäs gård
3317	1-87	Cadastre	
	88-97	Receipts	
3318	1-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3319	1-2	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	3-4	Miscellaneous	Anno 1568 & 1569; lönings register
	5-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	74-82	Register on fines	
	83-102	Receipts	
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1571			880 fol.
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327	Jören Jacobsson	District bailiwick	438 fol.
3320	1-116	Main account	
3321	1-6	Storage account	
	7-10	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	11-15	Miscellaneous	Helsingfors; lönings register
	16-22	Receipts	
3322	1	Miscellaneous	Misplaced folio
	2-4	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	5-19	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	20-29	Miscellaneous	Utfodringen
3323	1-67	Cadastre	
	68-79	Tenant farms	
	80-87	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	88-95	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	96-109	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	110-119	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	120-125	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll
	126-132	Ecclesiastical rec.	Kyrkslätt socken
	133-137	Ecclesiastical rec.	Victis socken
	138-147	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
3324	1-124	Additional taxes	s "Silver tax" records
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321	Henrik Henriksson	District bailiwick	442 fol.
3325	1-87	Main account	f. 81-82: mantalet
	88-93	Storage account	
	94	Miscellaneous	
	95-97	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
3326	1-20	Mantals register	
	21-30	Miscellaneous	Utspisningen
	31-40	Register on fines	
3327	1-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3328	1-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	66-70	Register on fines	
	71-72	Miscellaneous	
3329	1-174	Additional taxes	s "Silver tax" records
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1572			567 fol.
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327	Nils Mikaelsson	District bailiwick	54 fol.
3330	1-2; 51	Receipts	
	3-50; 52-54	Main account	

325	Rasmus Jönsson	Estate bailiwick	105 fol.
3331	1-36	Main account	19.1.–30.9.1572
	37-41	Storage account	
	42-44	Inventory	s Borgå gård 19.1.1572
	45-48	Inventory	s Helsingfors gård 4.2.1572
	49-51	Inventory	s Esbo gård 9.2.1572
	52-55	Inventory	s Borgå 1.10.1572
	56-60	Inventory	s Helsingfors gård 6.10.1572
	61-63	Inventory	s Esbo gård 9.10.1572
3332	1-18	Miscellaneous	Förtärningen, Esbo gård
	19-22	Mantals register	Esbo gård
	23-24	Mantals register	
	25-32	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	33-34	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	35-42	Receipts	
325/327	Nils Mikaelsson / Rasmus Jönsson	District / estate bailiwick	53 fol.
3333	1-25	Receipts	
	26-40	Miscellaneous	Utspisningen
3334	1-6	Inventory	s Helsingfors gård, till anno 1572
	7-10	Inventory	s Esbo gård, till anno 1572
	11-13	Inventory	s Borgå gård, till anno 1572
327	Nils Mikaelsson	District bailiwick	156 fol.
3335	1-76	Cadastre	
	77-82	Tenant farms	
	83-97	Cadastre	
	98-104	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	105-112	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	113-118	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll
	119-124	Ecclesiastical rec.	Kyrkslätt socken
	125-128	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sjundeå socken
	129-138	Ecclesiastical rec.	Qto Lojo socken
	139-147	Register on fines	
	148-156	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
329	Henrik Larsson	District bailiwick	199 fol.
3336	1-66	Main account	F. 58-65: additional taxes
	67-93	Miscellaneous	s Utspisning
3337	1-44	Cadastre	
	45-51	Register on fines	
	52-76	Receipts	
	77-86	Ecclesiastical rec.	Weckelax socken, Itis kyrko län
	87-96	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pyttis socken
	97-106	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
1573			515 fol.
327	Nils Mikaelsson	District bailiwick	59 fol.
3338	1; 4-44	Main account	
	2-3	Receipts	s
	45-48	Parson tax account	
	49-59	Additional tax account	

325	Rasmus Jönsson	Estate bailiwick	59 fol.
3339	1-26	Main account	
	27-30	Storage account	
	31-47	Miscellaneous	Förtärning, utspisning
	48-49	Mantals register	
	50-55	Receipts	
	56-57	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	58-59	Bailiff's concept	Skuld register
327	Nils Mikaelsson	District bailiwick	206 fol.
3340	1-30	Miscellaneous	Utspisning
3341	1-65	Cadastre	
	66-71	Tenant farms	
	72-75	Tenant farms	Fräses landbönder
	76-86	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
	87-96	Register on fines	
	97-104	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	105-110	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	111-120	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	121-126	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll
	127-132	Ecclesiastical rec.	Kyrkslätt socken
	133-138	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sjundeå socken
	139-146	Ecclesiastical rec.	Lojo socken
	147-176	Receipts	
Raseborgs län	Her Henrik	Province	5 fol.
3341a	1-5	Additional taxes	Silver tax
329	Henrik Larsson	District bailiwick	186 fol.
3342	1-61	Main account	F. 56-58: additional taxes
	62-81	Miscellaneous	Utspisning/utfodring
3343	1-40	Cadastre	
	41-47	Tenant farms	
	48-55	Register on fines	
	56-75	Receipts	
3344	1-7	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Veckelax socken
	8-10	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Itis präst gäll
	11-20	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pyttis socken
	21-30	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Perno socken. Seal?
1574			623 fol.
327	Clemet Eriksson	District bailiwick	45 fol.
3345	1-45	Main account	
325	Rasmus Jönsson	Estate bailiwick	69 fol.
3346	1-30; 68-69	Main account	
	31-34	Storage account	
	35-53	Miscellaneous	Förtärings (etc.) register
	54-58	Mantals register	Including lönings register
	59-67	Receipts	

327	Clemet Eriksson	District bailiwick	172 fol.
3347	1-44	Cadastre	Including some ecclesiastical taxes
	45-52	Tenant farms	
	53-61	Miscellaneous	s Ödes register
	62-76	Register on fines	
	77-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	85-91	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	92-102	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	103-109	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	110-115	Receipts	
3348	1-27	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	28-57	Receipts	
321	Lars Matsson	District bailiwick	337 fol.
3349	1-54	Main account	
	55-57	Parson tax account	
	58-65	Additional tax account	
3350	1-49	Cadastre	
	50-51	Tenant farms	
	52-59	Register on fines	
3351	1-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	62-93	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
3352	1-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	48-62	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	63-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	A
	65-87	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3353	1-33	Receipts	
1575			500 fol.
327	Clemet Eriksson	District bailiwick	47 fol.
3354	1-47	Main account	
325	Rasmus Jönsson	Estate bailiwick	77 fol.
3355	1-26	Estate account	
	27-37	Storage account	f. 31-37 empty
	38-45	Receipts	
3356	1-30	Mantals register	Inc. veckekost
	31-32	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
327	Clemet Eriksson	District bailiwick	127 fol.
3357	1-42	Cadastre	
	43-48	Tenant farms	
	49-56	Register on fines	
	57-63	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	64-69	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	70-81	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	82-89	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
3358	1-10	Miscellaneous	
	11-38	Receipts	
321	Lars Matsson	District bailiwick	249 fol.
3359	1-61	Main account	
3360	1-51	Cadastre	
	52-56	Tenant farms	
3361	1-67	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	68-82	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
3362	1-8	Register on fines	
	9-50	Receipts	

1576		607 fol.	
327	Clemet Eriksson	District bailiwick 258 fol.	
3363	1-54	Main account	f. 41-51: Borgå och Vik gårdar
	55-58	Inventory	s Borgå gård
	59-61	Inventory	s Vik gård
	62-64	Inventory	s Esbo gård
	65-67	Inventory	Borgå gård
	68-70	Inventory	Vik gård
	71-72	Inventory	Borgå gård, till anno 1577 (2.11.1576)
	73-75	Inventory	s Vik gård, till anno 1577 (4.10.1576 / 28.9.1576 (f. 75r))
	76-77	Miscellaneous	Lönings register. Vik gård
3364	1-42	Cadastre	
	43-48	Tenant farms	
	49-54	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	55-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	60-74	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	75-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	85-94	Register on fines	
	95-143; 148	Receipts	
	144-147	Miscellaneous	A Ödes gods
	149-170	Miscellaneous	A Utspisning etc.
	171-173	Receipts	s
	174-181	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
321	Lars Matsson	District bailiwick 349 fol.	
3365	1-60	Main account	
	61-73	Estate account	Esbo gård
	74-79	Storage account	Esbo gård
	80-84	Miscellaneous	Frälse bönder
3366	1-45	Cadastre	
	46-48	Tenant farms	
3367	1-6	Ecclesiastical rec.	Tenala socken
	7-11	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pojo socken
	12-16	Ecclesiastical rec.	Kisko kapellgäll
	17-19	Ecclesiastical rec.	Karislojo kapellgäll
	20-26	Ecclesiastical rec.	Lojo socken
	27-31	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sjundeå socken
	32-36	Ecclesiastical rec.	Kyrkslätt socken
	37-42	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo socken
	43-78	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	79-89	Register on fines	
	90-101	Miscellaneous	Esbo gård
	102-107	Inventory	s Esbo gård
3368	1-60	Ecclesiastical rec.	
3369	1-46	Receipts	s
	47-50	Inventory	s Esbo gård

1577		583 fol.	
327	Henrik Lydicksson	District bailiwick 264 fol.	
3370	1-44	Main account	
	45-63	Estate account	Borgå och Vik gårdar
3371	1-38	Cadastre	
	39-43	Tenant farms	
	44-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Helsinge socken
	52-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sibbo socken
	57-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Borgå socken
	74-80	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pernå socken
	81-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	Lappträsk kapellgäll
	85-92	Register on fines	
	93-96	Miscellaneous	s, A Burned farms
3372	1-6	Miscellaneous	s, A
	7-8	Inventory	Borgå gård
	9-12	Inventory	Vik gård
	13-17	Inventory	s Vik gård, till anno 1578
	18-19	Miscellaneous	Vik gård, lönings register
	20-27	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
	28-46	Miscellaneous	A Utspisnings register
3373	1-59	Receipts	s
321	Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick 319 fol.	
3374	1-61; 76-78	Main account	
	62-73	Estate account	Esbo gård
	74-75	Storage account	
3270a	1-50	Cadastre	
	51-53	Tenant farms	
3375	1-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	58-63	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Tenala socken
	64-67	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pojo socken
	68-71	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko socken
	72-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Karislojo socken
	74-83	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken
	84-89	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	90-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll
	95-98	Register on fines	
	99-111	Miscellaneous	s, A
3376	->	Receipts	F. 1-52; 57-58; 62-70; 76-77
	53-56	Inventory	s Esbo gård. Till anno 1578
	59-61	Inventory	Esbo gård. Till anno 1578
	71-74	Miscellaneous	Esbo gård. Utspisnings register
	75	Miscellaneous	Esbo gård. Lönings register

1578		535	
327	Henrik Lydicksson	District bailiwick	229 fol.
3377 1-49	Main account		
15	Receipts	s	
50-65	Estate account		Vik ladegård
3378 1-12	Miscellaneous		Restantie räkenskap
13-15	Receipts	s	
3379 1-34	Cadastre		
35-40	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd
41-45	Tenant farms		
46-52	Register on fines		
53-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
58-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken
71-76	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
77-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lappträsk kapellgäll
79-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
3380 1-65	Receipts	s	
321	Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick	306 fol.
3381 1-52	Main account		
53-63	Estate account		Esbo gård
64-67	Storage account		Esbo gård
3382 1-46	Cadastre		
47-48	Tenant farms		
49-53	Miscellaneous		Ödes längd
54-56	Register on fines		
57	Receipts	s	
58-63	Miscellaneous		Utspisnings register
64	Miscellaneous		Lönings register
65-71	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
72-75	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
76-79	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko socken. Anno 1579
80-81	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo socken
82-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå kapellgäll. Anno 1577
85-87	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå kapellgäll
88-97	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
98-102	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
103-107	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
108-177	Receipts		
3383 1-6	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd
7-10	Inventory	s	Esbo gård
11-62	Ecclesiastical rec.		

1579		589 fol.	
327	Lydick Nilsson	District bailiwick 258 fol.	
3384	1-55	Main account	
	56-67	Estate account	Vik ladugård
3385	1-44	Cadastre	
	45-50	Tenant farms	
	51-59	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
	60-69	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	70-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	79-83	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	84-92	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	93-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lappträsk kapellgäll
	95-101	Register on fines	
	102-141	Receipts	s
	142-183	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	184-186	Miscellaneous	
	187-189	Inventory	s Vik ladugård, 24.11.1578
	190	Miscellaneous	Vik ladugård, lönings register
	191	Receipts	
321	Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick 331 fol.	
3386	1-73	Main account	
	45-46	Receipts	s
	74-85	Estate account	Esbo gård
	86-87	Storage account	Esbo gård
3387	1-43	Cadastre	
	44-45	Tenant farms	
	46-49	Register on fines	s
	50-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Tenala socken
	57-62	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko kapellgäll
	63-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Karislojo annexa
	65-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sjundeå socken
	69-74	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	75-80	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll
	81-87	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken
	88-92	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
	93; 95-98	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	94	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	99-102	Inventory	s Esbo gård
3388	1-48	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	49-142	Receipts	s

1580		648 fol.	
327	Lydick Nilsson	District bailiwick	59 fol.
3389	1-56	Main account	
	57-59	Receipts	s
321	Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick	422 fol.
3390	1-2	Miscellaneous	A
	3-79; 93-95	Main account	
	52	Receipts	s
	80-90	Estate account	Esbo gård
	88	Receipts	s
	91-92	Storage account	
3391	1-43	Cadastre	
	44-45	Tenant farms	
	46-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Tenala socken
	54-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko kapellgäll
	58-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Karislojo annexa
	60-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken
	74-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sjundeå socken
	79-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	85-91	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll
	92-97	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pojo socken
	98-101	Register on fines	
	102-111	Miscellaneous	s Ödes längd
	112-115	Inventory	s Esbo gård
3392	1-50	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	51-200; 205-212	Receipts	s
	201-204r	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	204v	Miscellaneous	Lönings register, Esbo gård
329	Knut Glad	District bailiwick	167 fol.
3393	1-65	Main account	
	66-73	Estate account	Kymmene gård
	74-75	Inventory	Kymmene gård
	76	Miscellaneous	Lönings register, Kymmene gård
3394	1-30r	Cadastre	
	30v-37	Tenant farms	
	38-45	Register on fines	
	46-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Vederlaks socken
	48-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Vekkelaks socken
	54-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	Elimä kyrkelän
	57-66	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pyttis socken
	67-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	Lappträsk kapellgäll
	71-91	Receipts	

1581		763 fol.	
327	Lydick Nilsson	District bailiwick 322 fol.	
3395	1-2	Miscellaneous	A
	3-66	Main account	
	67-78	Estate account	Vik ladugård
	78-79	Receipts	
3396	1-2	Miscellaneous	N.B! 1565-66
	3-43	Cadastre	
	44-52	Tenant farms	
	53-57	Register on fines	
	58-70	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
	71-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsinge socken
	79-82	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	83-92	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	93-100	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pernå socken
	101-102	Ecclesiastical rec.	Lappträsk kapellgäll
	103	Miscellaneous	Lönings register, Vik ladugård
	104-163	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
3397	1-79	Receipts	s
321	Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick 441 fol.	
3398	1-69	Main account	
	14	Receipts	s
	70-83	Estate account	
	84-85	Storage account	
3399	->	Receipts	s F. 1-151; 158-160; 163; 165-178
	152-157	Register on fines	s, A
	161-162	Mantals register	A
	164	Miscellaneous	
	179-183	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register + lönings register
3400	1-47	Cadastre	
	48-50	Tenant farms	
3401	1-48	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	49-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Tenala socken
	57-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko kapellgäll
	62-63	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Karislojo socken
	64-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken
	73-81	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken, 1582!
	82-88	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sjundeå socken, 1581 and 1582
	89-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll
	95-100	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	101-109	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pojo socken, 1581 and 1582
	110-111	Miscellaneous	s Ödes längd, Tenala socken
	112-113	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Pojo socken
	114-115	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Karis socken
	116	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Ingo socken
	117-118	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Kyrkslätt socken
	119-120	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Esbo socken
	121-123	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Lojo socken

1582		306 fol.	
321	Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick	306 fol.
3402	1-2	Miscellaneous	
	3-5	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	6	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	7-9	Inventory	s
	10-11	Miscellaneous	
	12-14	Inventory	s
	15-87	Main account	
	88-103	Estate account	Esbo gård
	104-105	Storage account	Esbo gård
	73; 100-102	Receipts	s
3403	1-13	Arrears account	
	14-41	Receipts	s
3404	1-39r	Cadastre	
	39v-41	Tenant farms	
	42-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	48-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	54-58	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	59-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
3405	1-46	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll Kyrkslätt socken Kisko kapellgäll Tenala socken
	47-96	Receipts	

1583		337 fol.	
321	Henrik Eriksson	District bailiwick	337 fol.
3406	1-91; 113	Main account	
	92-94	Receipts	s
	95-110	Estate account	Esbo gård
	111-112	Storage account	Esbo gård
	114-123	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto
	124-139	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	140-145	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	146-151	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	152-157	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sjundeå socken, 1583 and 1584
	158-160	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	161-163	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
3407	1-49r	Cadastre	Lojo socken, 1583 and 1584
	49v-54	Tenant farms	Tenala socken
	55-108	Ecclesiastical rec.	Esbo kapellgäll
	109-174	Receipts	s

1584				401 fol.
321	Henrik Eriksson	District bailiwick		401 fol.
3408	1-75; 96	Main account		
	66; 83	Receipts	s	
	76-93	Estate account		Esbo gård
	94-95	Storage account		Esbo gård
3409	1-8	Miscellaneous		
	9-10	Miscellaneous	s	
	11-15	Miscellaneous	s	
	16-19	Miscellaneous	s	
	20-25	Miscellaneous	s	
	26-31	Receipts		
3410	1-67	Cadastre		
	68-82	Ecclesiastical rec.		Sjundeå socken
	83-87	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	88-93	Ecclesiastical rec.		Esbo kapellgäll
	94-96	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	97-100	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäll
	101-105	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	106-111	Register on fines	s	
	112-123	Ödes längd	s	
3411	1-44	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	45-48	Miscellaneous	A	Månads kost / förtärnings register, Esbo gård
	49-52	Miscellaneous	A	Lönings register, Esbo gård
	53-151	Receipts	s	

1585				378 fol.
327	Tomas Henriksson	District bailiwick		150 fol.
3412	1-54	Main account		
3413	1-41	Cadastre		
	42-50	Tenant farms		
	51	Mantals register		
	52-62	Receipts		
	63-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
	69-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
	73-83	Ecclesiastical rec.		Borgå socken
	84-91	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
	92-93	Ecclesiastical rec.		Lappträsk kapellgäll
	94-96	Register on fines		

321	Hans Kielk		District bailiwick	228 fol.
3414	1-91	Main account		
	92-106	Estate account		Esbo gård
	107-112	Storage account		Esbo gård
3415	1-49	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	50-53	Miscellaneous	A	Lönings register, Esbo gård
3416	1-6	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	7-12	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	13-17	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäll
	18-19	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo annexa
	20-27	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
	28-31	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
	32-35	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	36-41	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
	42-57	Receipts		
	58-63	Miscellaneous	A	
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1586				644 fol.
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327	Tomas Henriksson		District bailiwick	11 fol.
3417	1-11	Arrears account		1585-1587
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327	Tomas Henriksson		District bailiwick	349 fol.
3418	1-58	Main account		
	59	Receipts	s	
3419	1-42	Cadastre		
	43-44	Mantals register		Helsingefors gård
	45-60	Tenant farms		Folios missing
	61-66	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
	67-69	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
	70-82	Ecclesiastical rec.		Borgå socken
	83-88	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
	89-90	Ecclesiastical rec.		Lapträsk kapellgäll
	91-98	Register on fines		
	99-141	Additional taxes		F. 135-141: tenants
	142-165	Receipts	s	
3419a	1-86	Cadastre		Revisory cadastre
	87-125	Cadastre		

321	Hans Kielk		District bailiwick	284 fol.
3420 1-88	Main account			
63	Receipts	s		
89-110; 113	Estate account			Esbo gård
111-112	Storage account			Esbo gård
114-117	Inventory			10.10.1586, Esbo gård
3421 1-42r	Cadastre			
42v-44	Tenant farms			
3422 1-6	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Tenala socken
7-10	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Pojo socken
11-14	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Kisko kapellgäll
15-16	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Karislojo annexa
17-24	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Lojo socken
25-28	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Sjundeå socken
29-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Kyrkslätt socken
34-39	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Esbo kapellgäll
40-43	Miscellaneous	s		Ödes längd, Kyrkslätt socken
42	Receipts	s		
44-45	Miscellaneous	s		Ödes längd, Sjundeå socken
46-47	Miscellaneous	s		Ödes längd, Lojo socken
48	Receipts	s		
49-50	Miscellaneous	s		Ödes längd, Pojo socken
51-52	Miscellaneous	s		Ödes längd, Tenala socken
53-54	Miscellaneous	s		Ödes längd, Esbo socken
55-73	Receipts	s		
3423 1-50	Ecclesiastical rec.			
1587				527 fol.
327	Tomas Henriksson		District bailiwick	243 fol.
3424 1-60	Main account			
61-66	Miscellaneous			Borgläger gård, 1585-1587
67-72	Miscellaneous	A		
73-80	Miscellaneous	A		
81	Arrears account			Headline folio for KA 3417
3425 1-38	Cadastre			
39-55	Tenant farms			
56-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Helsinge socken
62-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Sibbo socken
66-76	Ecclesiastical rec.			Borgå socken
77-79	Ecclesiastical rec.			Mäntsälä "ny cappell län"
80-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Pernå socken
86-88	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Sankt Lars kapellgäll (Lappträsk)
89-93	Register on fines	s		
94-98	Miscellaneous			1585-1587
99-160	Receipts	s		
161-162	Miscellaneous	s		Lönings register, Helsingefors gård

321		Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick	284 fol.
3426	1-75	Main account		
	76-88	Estate account		
	89-91	Storage account		
	91a	Receipts	s	
3427	1-6	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	7-8	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	9-12	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäll
	13-14	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo annexa
	15-24	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
	25-27	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
	28-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	34-36	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
	37-38	Miscellaneous		Utspisnings register
	39-41	Miscellaneous		Månads kost
	42	Miscellaneous		Lönings register
	43-46	Inventory	s	10.10.1586, Esbo gårdh
	47-48	Register on fines	s	
	49-52	Inventory	s	5.10.1587(?), Esbo gårdh
	53-55	Miscellaneous	s	
	56-59	Miscellaneous	s	
	60	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Pojo socken
	61	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Esbo socken
	62-65	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Tenala socken
	66	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Kisko bol
	67-68	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Pojo socken
	69	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Sjundeå
	70	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Karislojo kapellgäll
	71-73	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Lojo socken
	74-76	Receipts	s	
	77; 82-83	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Karis socken
	78-81	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Ingo socken
3428	1-55	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	56-84; 88-111	Receipts	s	
	85-87	Miscellaneous		
1588				988 fol.
327		Gabriel Matsson	District bailiwick	186 fol.
3429	1-61	Main account		
	20; 34; 36; 46	Receipts	s	
3430	1-36	Arrears account		
	37-59	Arrears	A	
	60-68	Register on fines	A	
	69-87	Additional taxes	A	
	88-91	Mantals register	A	
	92-125	Receipts	s	

328	Henrik Larsson	District bailiwick	114 fol.
3431	1-29	Estate account	Helsingefors gård
	30-31	Inventory	s Vik ladugård, 16.3.1588
	32-33	Inventory	s Helsingefors gård, 8.1.1587
	34-35	Inventory	s Helsingefors gård, 15.1.1589
	36-37	Inventory	s Vik ladugård, 26.1.1589
	38-44	Receipts	
3432	1-2	Miscellaneous	s, A
	3-44	Mantals register	
3433	1-13	Miscellaneous	Helsingefors gård, Förtärnings register etc.
	14-26	Miscellaneous	Vik ladegård, Utspisnings register etc.
327	Gabriel Matsson	District bailiwick	164 fol.
3434	1-44	Cadastre	
	45-58	Tenant farms	
	59-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	Helsing socken
	66-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	71-80	Ecclesiastical rec.	Borgå socken
	81-82	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto Mäntsälä nykapell
	83-88	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pernå socken
	89-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sankt Lars kapellgäll (Lappträsk)
	91-97	Register on fines	
	98-158	Receipts	s
	159-164	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
321	Olof Ångerman	District bailiwick	362 fol.
3435	1-84	Main account	
	85-97r	Estate account	Esbo gård
	97v-100	Storage account	Esbo gård
	101-105	Miscellaneous	Utspisnings register
	106	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	107-108	Miscellaneous	Längd på järn
	109-112	Inventory	12.10.1589, Esbo gård
3436	1-52	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	53-158*	Receipts	s
	127; 130-132	Miscellaneous	s
3437	1-53	Cadastre	Revisory cadastre
	54-55	Register on fines	s
	56-62	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Tenala socken, 1588
	63-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pojo socken, 1588
	65-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko kapellgäll, 1588
	69-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sjundeå socken, 1588
	73-74	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Karislojo annexa, 1588
	75-80	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kysklätt socken, 1588
	81-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll, 1588
	85-92	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken, 1588
361	Jöran Andersson	Tenant bailiwick	62 fol.
3438	1-33	Main account	
	5	Receipts	s
	34-39	Tenant account	
	40-45	Miscellaneous	Kvarn tull peningar
	46-49	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	50-51	Miscellaneous	
	52-57	Receipts	
	58-62	Miscellaneous	
	61	Receipts	

329	Jöran Jönsson	District bailiwick	100 fol.
3439 1-53	Main account		
54-55	Register on fines		
56-57	Parson taxes		
58-63	Additional taxes		
64-85	Estate account		Kymmene gård
86-91	Mantals register	A	Kymmene gård
92-95	Inventory	s	28.9.1587, Kymmene gård
96-100	Inventory	s	28.9.1588, Kymmene gård

1589 682 fol.

327	Henrik Jönsson	District bailiwick	296 fol.
3440 1-64	Main account		
65-80	Estate account		
3441 1-39	Cadastre		
40-42	Miscellaneous		Ödes längd
43-46	Tenant farms		Längden över adelns landbönder
47-51	Miscellaneous	A	Jöran Andersson landbogofde
52-58	Tenant farms		
59-62	Register on fines		
63-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
69-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
74-85	Ecclesiastical rec.		Borgå socken
86-93	Ecclesiastical rec.		Pernå socken
94-95	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Mäntsälä
96-97	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lapträsk
98-127; 134	Receipts		
128-133	Cadastre	A	Kaukjärvi fjärding, 1589–1590
135	Miscellaneous		
136-139	Tenant farms	A	Restantie register
140	Miscellaneous		Lönings register, Helsingefors & Vik ladegårdar
141	Mantals register	A	Helsingefors gård
142-146	Tenant farms	A	
147-152	Inventory	s	15.1.1588, Helsingefors gård; 16.1.1588 Viks gård
153-173	Miscellaneous		
174-196	Receipts	s	
3442 1-20	Miscellaneous		

321	Olof Ångerman		District bailiwick	375 fol.
3443	1-88	Main account		
	89-101	Estate account		Esbo gård
	102-105	Storage account		Esbo gård
	106-108	Miscellaneous		Månads kost
	109-111	Miscellaneous		Utspisnings register
	112-113	Miscellaneous		Lönings register
	114-115	Miscellaneous	A	Dagsvärks register
	116-119	Inventory	s	Esbo gård
	120-121	Miscellaneous		
3444	1-69	Cadastre		
	70-73	Register on fines		
	74-129	Receipts	s	
3445	1-44	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	45-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
	57-60	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
	61-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	65-67	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
	68-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	74-75	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	76-77	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo annexa
	78-81	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäll
	82-108; 124-125	Receipts	s	
	109-123	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längder
361	Jöran Andersson		Tenant bailiwick	11 fol.
3446	1-11	Main account		
	6-7	Receipts	s	
1590				603 fol.
327	Henrik Jönsson		District bailiwick	236 fol.
3447	1-63	Main account		
	64-82	Estate account		
3448	1-39	Cadastre		
	40-45	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
	46-50	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
	51-63	Ecclesiastical rec.		Borgå socken
	64-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
	71-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	S:t Mats kapellgäld
	73-150*; 154	Receipts	s	
	125-130	Register on fines		
	151	Miscellaneous		
	152-153	Tenant farms	A	

321	Olof Ångerman		District bailiwick	367 fol.
3449	1-23	Miscellaneous		
	24-108	Main account		
	109-122	Estate account		Esbo gård
	123-125	Storage account		Esbo gård
	126-129	Inventory	s	Esbo gård
	130-134r	Miscellaneous		Utspisnigs längd
	134v-137	Miscellaneous		Månads kost
	138	Miscellaneous		Lönings register
	139-140	Miscellaneous	A	Dagsvärker
	141-142	Miscellaneous		Taxerings register
	143-144	Register on fines		
3450	1-71	Cadastre		
3451	1-44	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	45-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	52-54	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	55-58	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäld
	59-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
	65-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäld
	69-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	73-76	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
	77-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo socken
	79-152	Receipts	s	

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287 fol.

321	Henrik Eriksson		District bailiwick	287 fol.
3452	1-73	Main account		
	74-85	Estate account		Esbo gård
	86-88	Storage account		Esbo gård
3453	1-44	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	45-99	Receipts	s	
	100-103	Inventory		Esbo gård
	104-108	Miscellaneous		Månads kost
	109-112	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	113-116	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Inc. 1592; Pojo socken
	117-118	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo socken
	119-126	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Inc. 1592; Kisko kapellgäld
	127-132	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
	133-136	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	137-139	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
	140-142	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	1592; Esbo kapellgäll
	143-145	Register on fines	s, A	
	146	Miscellaneous	s, A	"Styremans vinter kost"
	147-148	Miscellaneous		Mantal längd
	149-150	Miscellaneous		Lönings register
	151-152	Miscellaneous		
	153-158	Miscellaneous		Taxerings längd
	159-199	Receipts	s	

1592		706 fol.	
327	Lydik Henriksson	District bailiwick 203 fol.	
3454	1-65	Main account	
	66-73	Estate account	Helsingefors gård och Vik ladugård
	74-76	Miscellaneous	Lönings register; Helsingefors gård och Vik ladugård
3455	1-44	Cadastre	
	45-58	Tenant farms	
	59-62	Register on fines	s
	61	Receipts	s
	63-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Helsinge socken
	69-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sibbo socken
	73-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Borgå socken
	85	Receipts	
	86-93	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	94-95	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lappträsk kapellgäll
	96-127	Receipts	
321	Henrik Eriksson	District bailiwick 285 fol.	
3456	1-67	Main account	
	68-78	Estate account	Esbo gård
	79-82	Storage account	
3457	1-69	Cadastre	
	70	Receipts	
3458	1-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	52-87; 90-94	Receipts	
	88-89	Miscellaneous	A
	95-100	Register on fines	s, A
	101-104	Inventory	
	105-106	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	107-111	Miscellaneous	Månads koster
	112-115	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Tenala socken
	116-117	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Karislojo annexa
	118-123	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken
	124-127	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	128-133	Receipts	
329	Hans Bertilsson	District bailiwick 218 fol.	
3459	1-64	Main account	
	65-82; 85-87	Estate account	Kymmene gård
	83-84	Receipts	
	88-103	Miscellaneous	Mantals (/förtärnings) register
	93; 100	Receipts	s
	104	Miscellaneous	Lönings register
	105-106	Miscellaneous	Fragmentary storage record?
	107-144	Receipts	
3460	1-12	Ecclesiastical rec.	Qto Pyttis och Elimä socken
	13-16	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	17-20	Ecclesiastical rec.	Vederlaks socken
	21-22	Ecclesiastical rec.	Lappträsk kapellgäll
	23-27	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Veckelaks socken
	28-30	Miscellaneous	A Ödes spanmål
	31-38	Miscellaneous	A
	39-40	Register on fines	
	41-73	Cadastre	F. 63v-68: tenants
	74	Receipts	

1593		603 fol.	
327	Lydik Henriksson	District bailiwick 334 fol.	
3461	1-113	Main account	
	114-125	Estate account	Helsingfors herregård och Vik ladugård
	126-129	Miscellaneous	önings register, Helsingfors herregård och Vik ladugård
	130-131	Inventory	16.3.1592, Helsingfors herregård
3462	1-41	Cadastre	
	42-55	Tenant farms	
	56-57	Receipts	s
	58-66	Miscellaneous	s Ödes längd
	67-112	Miscellaneous	Gärde manttall
	113-167	Receipts	s
	168-174	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Helsinge socken
	175-178	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sibbo socken
	179-189	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Borgå socken
	190-197	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Perno socken
	198	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	199-201	Ecclesiastical rec.	Mäntsälä ny kapellgäll
	202-203	Receipts	
321	Lars Jönsson	District bailiwick 269 fol.	
3463	1-96	Main account	
	97-113	Additional tax account	Krigs folks gården
3464	1-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	62-66	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko kapellgäll
	67-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	71-74	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Tenala socken
	75-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pojo socken
	79-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Inc. 1594. Sjundeå socken
	85-87	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll
	88-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s 1594, Esbo kapellgäll
	91-156	Receipts	s
1594		445 fol.	
327	Lydik Henriksson	District bailiwick 202 fol.	
3465	1-57	Main account	
	58-69r	Estate account	Helsingfors gård och Vik ladugård
	69v-71	Inventory	Helsingfors herregård
	72-73	Miscellaneous	Lönings register, Helsingfors gård och Vik ladugård
3466	1-40	Cadastre	
	41-55	Tenant farms	
	56-57	Register on fines	s
	58-61	Register on fines	s Anno 1593
	62-63	Register on fines	s Anno 1592–1594, Helsingfors stad
	64-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Helsinge socken
	69-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sibbo socken
	73-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Borgå socken
	86-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pernå socken
	95-96	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lappträsk kapellgäll
	97-129	Receipts	

321		Lars Jönsson	District bailiwick 243 fol.	
3467	1-99	Main account		
3468	1-52	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	53-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	57-60	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	61-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäll
	66	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Sjundeå socken
	67	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Karislojo kapellgäll
	68-71	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Pojo socken
	72-73	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Esbo socken
	74-75	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Lojo socken
	76-77	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Kyrkslätt socken
	78-79	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Tenala socken
	80-81	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Karis socken
	82-83	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1593–1594, poverty exceptions, Ingo socken
	84-144	Receipts		

1595 329 fol.

321		Lars Jönsson	District bailiwick 329 fol.	
3469	1-109	Main account		
	110-119	Receipts		
3470	1-62	Cadastre		
	63	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Tenala socken
	64	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Pojo socken
	65	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Sjundeå socken
	66	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Karislojo kapellgäll
	67-69	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Kisko bol
	70-71	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Kyrkslätt socken
	72-73	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Lojo socken
	74-77	Miscellaneous	s	Poverty exceptions, Esbo socken
	78-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1595–1596; Sjundeå socken
	85-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1595–1596; Kisko kapellgäll
	91-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	95-98	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	99-100	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo annexa
	101-104	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1595–1596; Tenala socken
	105-107	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
	108-110	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1596; Esbo kapellgäll
	111-120	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1595–1596; Lojo socken
3471	1-58	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	59-90	Receipts	s	

1596 220 fol.

321		Lars Jönsson	District bailiwick 220 fol.	
3472	1-90	Main account		
3473	1-57	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	58-65	Receipts	s	
	66-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lojo socken
	74-77	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	78-81	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pojo socken
	82-124	Receipts	s	
	125-130	Miscellaneous	A	

1597				
NO RECORDS				
1598				
				289 fol.
327	Olof Jacobsson		District bailiwick 289 fol.	
3474	1-83	Main account		
	84-94	Estate account		Helsingfors gård
3475	1-44	Cadastre		
	45-48	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
	49-55	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
	56-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lapträsk kapellgåll
	58	Receipts	s	
	59-63	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
	64-73	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken
	74	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Mäntsälä kapell länn
	75-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1599; Borgå socken
	85-92	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd; Borgå länn
	93-97	Register on fines		
	98-110	Tenant farms		
	111-116	Receipts	s	
3476	1-28	Arrears	s	Helsinge socken
	29-47	Arrears	s	Sibbo socken
	48-58	Arrears		Borgå socken
	59-71	Arrears		Pernå socken
	72-75	Register on fines		
	76-79	Miscellaneous	s	
1599				
				906 fol.
327	Olof Jacobsson		District bailiwick 697 fol.	
3477	1-85	Main account		
	86-96	Estate account		Helsingefors gård
3478	1-25	Miscellaneous		
3479	1-42	Cadastre		Anno 1598(?)
	43-48	Tenant farms		Anno 1598
3480	1-38	Cadastre		
	39-56	Tenant farms		
	57-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
	62-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
	66	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lapträsk socken
	67-74	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
	75-78	Inventory	s	15.7.1597
	79-244	Receipts	s	
3481	1-183	Receipts	s	
3482	1-14	Arrears	s	Gården, 1599(?), Pernå socken
	15-30	Arrears	s, A	Gården, 1600(?), Pernå socken
	31-38	Arrears	s, A	Skatten, 1600, Pernå socken
	39-48	Arrears	s, A	Smöret, 1601, Pernå socken
	59-84	Arrears	s, A	1600, 1601, Borgå socken
	85-93	Arrears	s	Helsinge socken
	94-101	Arrears	s	1600, 1601, Sibbo socken

329		Hans Bertilsson		District bailiwick 209 fol.	
3483	1-35	Main account			
	36-45	Estate account			Kymmenegård
	46	Mantals register			Anno 1598
	47	Mantals register			Anno 1599
3484	1-6	Miscellaneous	s, A		Ödes register, Veckelaks socken
	7-11	Miscellaneous	s, A		Ödes register, Vederlaks socken
	12-15	Miscellaneous	s, A		Ödes register, Pyttis socken
	16-48	Cadastre			
	49-52	Tenant farms			
	53-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Vederlaks socken
	58-61	Ecclesiastical rec.			Elimä kapellgäll
	62-71	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto		Pyttis och Elimä kapellgäll
	72-75	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto		Lappträsk
	76-152	Receipts	s		
1600				1269 fol.	

327		Hans Wirtenberg von Debern		District bailiwick 377 fol.	
3485	1-50	Main account			
3486	1-26	Cadastre			
	27-38	Tenant farms			
	39-40	Annual taxes			
	41-43	Miscellaneous			Ödes längd
	44-48	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Helsinge socken
	49-52	Ecclesiastical rec.			Sibbo socken
	53-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto		Borgå socken
	66-71	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Pernå socken
	72-76	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto		Lappträsk
	77-216	Receipts	s		
	217-238	Additional taxes			
	239-290	Miscellaneous	A		
	291-327	Receipts	s		

321	Lars Jönsson		District bailiwick	617 fol.
3487	1-62	Main account		Shortened version?
3488	1-105	Main account		
3489	1-15	Estate account		Esbo gård
	16-20	Inventory	s	30.8.1599, Esbo gård
	21-24	Inventory	s	11(?).10.1600, Esbo gård
	25-29	Miscellaneous		Utspisnigs längd, Esbo gård
	30-33	Miscellaneous		Månads kost, Esbo gård
	34	Miscellaneous		Lönings register, Esbo gård
	35-54	Receipts	s	
3490	1-60	Cadastre		
	61-66	Miscellaneous	s	"Mantal eller röketall", Tenala socken
	67-74	Miscellaneous	s	"Mantal eller röketall", Pojo socken
	75-84	Miscellaneous	s	"Mantal eller röketall", Lojo socken
	85-90	Miscellaneous	s	"Mantal eller röketall", Sjundeå socken
	91-96	Miscellaneous	s	"Mantal eller röketall", Kyrkslätt socken
	97-103	Miscellaneous	s	"Mantal eller röketall", Esbo socken
	104-106	Additional taxes	s	Esbo socken
	108-109	Additional taxes	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	110-111	Additional taxes	s	Sjundeå socken
	112-113	Additional taxes	s	Pojo socken
	114-115r	Additional taxes	s	Karislojo kapellgäll
	115v-117	Additional taxes	s	Tenala socken
	118-122	Additional taxes	s	Lojo socken
	123-181; 192-	Receipts	s	
	182-191	Miscellaneous		
	197-202	Mantals register		
	203-208	Receipts	s	
3491	1-37	Ecclesiastical rec.		
	38-40	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	41-48	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
	49-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Tenala socken
	54-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Karislojo kapellgäll
	57-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
	60-62	Ecclesiastical rec.		Kisko kapellgäll
	63-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
	65-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt kapellgäll
	69-90	Receipts		
	91-188	Receipts	s	

327	Hans Wirtenberg von Debern	District bailiwick	275 fol.
3492 1-2	Mantals register	A	
3-56	Main account		
3493 1-35	Cadastre		
36-41	Tenant farms		
42-46	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Vederlax socken
47-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Pyttis och Elimä socknar
58-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Veckelax socken
65-118	Receipts	s	
119-145	Additional taxes		
146-151	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Veckelax socken
152-158r	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Vederlax socken
159r-162	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Pyttis socken
163-172	Arrears	s, A	Additional taxes, Veckelax socken
173-179	Arrears	s, A	Additional taxes, Vederlax socken
180-185	Arrears	s, A	Annual taxes, Vederlax socken
186-195	Arrears	s, A	Annual taxes, Veckelax socken
196-203	Arrears	s, A	Annual taxes, Pyttis socken
204-207	Arrears	s, A	Additional taxes, Pyttis socken
208-219	Receipts		

1601 1273 fol.

327	Hans Wirtenberg von Debern	District bailiwick	419 fol.
3494 1-57	Main account		
3495 1-26	Cadastre		
27-39r	Tenant farms		
39v-41	Miscellaneous		Ödes längd
42-44	Register on fines		
45-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
52-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Sibbo socken
60-75	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Borgå socken
76-77	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Lappträsk kapellgäll
78-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
86-241	Receipts	s	
242-273	Additional taxes		
274-307	Receipts	s	
3495a 1-55	Miscellaneous	s	Ransaknings längd

321	Nils Clemetsson	District bailiwick	547 fol.
3496	1-90	Main account	
	91-112	Additional tax account	
	113	Receipts	s
3497	1-88	Cadastre	
	89	Tenant farms	
	90-91	Receipts	
	92-94	Register on fines	s
	95-155	Receipts	s
	156-167	Miscellaneous	s
	168-171	Receipts	
3498	1-7	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Lojo socken
	8-13	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Kyrkslätt socken
	14-21	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Ingo socken
	22-29	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Karis socken
	30-37	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Pojo socken
	38-44	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Tenala socken
	45-49	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Sjundeå socken
	50-55	Miscellaneous	s "Mantal eller röketall", Esbo socken
	56-93	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	94-167	Receipts	
	168-171	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko kapellgäll
	172-189	Additional taxes	s, A Ingo socken
	190-195	Additional taxes	s, A Esbo socken
	196-199	Additional taxes	s, A Sjundeå socken
	200-201	Additional taxes	s, A Ingo socken
	202-205	Additional taxes	s, A Pojo socken
	206	Receipts	
	207-222	Additional taxes	s, A Karis socken
	223-224	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll
	225-228	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sjundeå socken
	229-232	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	233-242	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Lojo socken
	243-248	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Karis socken
	249-253	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Pojo socken
	254-259	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Ingo socken
	260-263	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Tenala socken

327		Hans Wirtenberg von Debern		District bailiwick	307 fol.
3499	1-52	Main account			
	53-64	Estate account		Anno 1600, Kymmenegård	
	65-74	Estate account		Kymmenegård	
	75-76	Mantals register			
3500	1-6r	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Veckelax socken	
	6v-10	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Vederlax socken	
	11-14	Miscellaneous	s, A	Ödes längd, Pyttis socken	
	15-17r	Arrears		Vederlax socken	
	17v-21	Arrears		Veckelax socken	
	22-26	Arrears		Pyttis socken	
	27-34	Arrears		Pyttis och Elimä socknar	
	35-40r	Arrears		Vederlax socken	
	40v-48	Arrears		Veckelax socken	
	49-81	Cadastre			
	82-87	Tenant farms			
	89-101	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Pyttis och Elimä socknar	
	102-107	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Vederlax socken	
	108-113	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Veckelax socken	
	114-116	Ecclesiastical rec.		Anno 1600, Itis kyrkgäll	
	117-120	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Anno 1600, Lappträsk kapellgäll	
	121-123	Ecclesiastical rec.		Itis kyrkgäll	
	124-127	Ecclesiastical rec.		Vederlax socken	
	128-135	Ecclesiastical rec.		Veckelax socken	
	136-145	Ecclesiastical rec.		Pyttis socken	
	146-231	Receipts	s		
1602					286 fol.
321		Nils Clemetsson		District bailiwick	286 fol.
3501	1-75	Main account			
	76-86	Estate account		Esbo gård	
	87-90	Mantals register		Esbo gård	
	91-92	Miscellaneous	s		
3502	1-57	Cadastre			
	58-68	Receipts			
	69-70	Mantals register	s, A		
	71-83	Receipts	s		
	84-85	Miscellaneous	A		
	86-100	Receipts	s		
	101-138	Ecclesiastical rec.			
	139-142	Miscellaneous		Ödes längd	
	143-146	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäll	
	147-151	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken	
	152-153	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll	
	154-155	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Vichtis socken	
	156-159	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken	
	160-162	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pojo socken	
	163-166	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Tenala socken	
	167-175	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lojo socken	
	176	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Esbo socken	
	177	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Kyrkslätt socken	
	178-183	Miscellaneous	s	Ödes längd, Lojo socken	
	184-189	Miscellaneous	A		
	190-194	Receipts	s		

1603		545 fol.	
327	Hans Wirtenberg von Debern	District bailiwick	226 fol.
3503	1-36	Cadastre	
	37-50	Tenant farms	
3504	1-106	Receipts	s
3505	1-7	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Anno 1602, Helsinge socken
	8-12	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Anno 1602(?), Nurmo kapellgäll
	13-20	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Sibbo socken
	21-40	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Borgå socken
	41-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Pernå socken
	57-59	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Pernå socken
	60-63	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Borgå socken
	64-66r	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Sibbo socken
	66v-69	Miscellaneous	s, A Ödes längd, Helsinge socken
	70	Receipts	s
321	Lars Mickelsson	District bailiwick	319 fol.
3506	1-37	Main account	
	38-40	Parson tax account	
	41-45	Additional tax account	
	46-54	Additional tax account	
3507	1-6	Miscellaneous	Ödes längd
	7	Receipts	s
	8-9	Register on fines	s
	10-12	Receipts	
	13-16	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kisko kapellgäll
	17-19	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sjundeå socken
	20-21	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo kapellgäll
	22-27	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Lojo socken
	28-31	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Kyrkslätt socken
	32-34	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Anno 1604, Kyrkslätt socken
	35-39	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Anno 1605, Kyrkslätt socken
	40-43	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Tenala socken
	44-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Pojo socken
	48-49	Miscellaneous	s Ödes längd, additional taxes, Lojo socken
	50-53	Miscellaneous	s Ödes längd, additional taxes, Pojo(?) socken
	54	Miscellaneous	s Ödes längd, additional taxes, Kyrkslätt socken
	55-56	Miscellaneous	s Ödes längd, additional taxes, Sjundeå socken
	57-63	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Tenala socken
	64-69	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Pojo socken
	70-73	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Karislojo kapellgäll
	74-81	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Lojo socken
	82-87	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Sjundeå socken
	88-93	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Kyrkslätt socken
	94-99	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Esbo socken
	100-105	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Karis socken
	106-111	Mantals register	s Additional taxes, Ingo socken
	112-265	Receipts	s

1604		1699 fol.	
327	Mikael Andersson	District bailiwick 792 fol.	
3508 1-47	Main account		
48-56	Additional tax account		
57-67	Estate account		Helsingfors gård och Vik ladugård
3509 1-372	Cadastre		
373-380	Tenant farms		
381	Receipts		
3510 1-266	Receipts	s	
267-274	Miscellaneous		
275-302	Receipts		
303-306	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Helsinge socken
307-310	Ecclesiastical rec.	Qto	Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
311-316	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Borgå socken
317-324	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
325-330	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Sibbo socken
331-332	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Lappträsk (kapellgäll)
333	Receipts		
334-337	Register on fines	s, A	
338-344	Receipts	s	

321	Lars Mikaelsson		District bailiwick	481 fol.
3511	1-12	Main account		
	13-22	Additional tax account		
3512	1-31; 36-45	Main account		
	32-35	Receipts	s	
3513	1-7	Miscellaneous		Pojo socken
	8-11	Miscellaneous		Kyrkslätt socken
	12-15	Miscellaneous		Esbo socken
	16-18	Miscellaneous		Lojo socken
	19-22	Miscellaneous		Sjundeå socken
	23-26	Miscellaneous		Tenala socken
3514	1-2	Miscellaneous		
	3-121	Receipts	s	
	122-125	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	126-127	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo kapellgäll
	128-131	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
	132-142	Receipts	s	
3515	1-6	Miscellaneous		Esbo socken
	7-30	Receipts	s	
	31-34	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko kapellgäll
	35-38	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Anno 1605, Lojo socken
	39-42	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1605, Pojo socken
	43-48	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1604-1605, Tenala socken
	49-52	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1605, Sjundeå socken
	53-54	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
	55-58	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1605, Karislojo kapellgäll
	59-66	Additional taxes	s	Tenala socken
	67-71	Additional taxes	s	Pojo socken
	72-77	Additional taxes	s	Karislojo kapellgäll
	78-85	Additional taxes	s	Lojo socken
	86-91	Additional taxes	s	Sjundeå socken
	92-97	Additional taxes	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	98-104	Additional taxes	s	Esbo socken
	105-106	Additional taxes	s	Karis socken
	107	Additional taxes	s	Ingo socken
	108-151	Receipts	s	
	152-157	Miscellaneous		Ödes längd
	158-174	Receipts	s	
	175-180	Additional taxes		
	181-182	Miscellaneous		
	183-246	Receipts	s	
329	Olof Andersson		District bailiwick	426 fol.
3516	1-40	Main account		
3517	1-16(?)	Miscellaneous	s, A	Odes längd; N.B.: Separate folio numbers
	1-211	Cadastre		
	212-217	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1605. Pyttis socken och Elime fjärding
	218-228	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1606. Pyttis socken och Elime fjärding
	229-245	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	
	246-247	Register on fines	s, A	Anno 1605
	248-251	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1605. Veckelax socken
	252-254	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1605. Vederlax socken
	255-258	Ecclesiastical rec.		Anno 1605. Itis kapellgäll
	259-264	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Anno 1605(?) och 1606(?). Kymmenegårds län
	265-370	Receipts	s	

1605				979 fol.
327	Salomon Jönsson			District bailiwick 431 fol.
3518	1-50	Main account		
	51-59	Estate account		Helsingfors herregård och Vik Ladugård
	60-61	Inventory	s	Helsingfors 27.9.1604
	62-63	Inventory	s	Helsingfors 2.11.1605
	64-65	Miscellaneous		
3519	1-87	Receipts	s	
	88-90	Miscellaneous	s	
	91-184	Receipts	s	
	185-186	Register on fines	s	
	187-198	Ecclesiastical rec.		Pernå socken
	199-204	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken och Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
	205-214	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1606, Borgå socken
	215-218	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sibbo socken
	219-222	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	223-305	Receipts	s	
	306-307	Miscellaneous	s	
	308-321	Receipts		
	322-328	Miscellaneous		
	329-356	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Borgå län
	357-366	Receipts	s	
321	Johan Jacobsson			District bailiwick 548 fol.
3520	1-43	Main account		Johannis 1605 – Johannis 1606
3521	1-14	Estate account		24.4.1605–24.4.1606, Esbo gård
	15-27	Estate account		24.4.1606–8.4.1607, Esbo gård
	28-29	Inventory	s	24.4.1605, Esbo gård
	30-33	Inventory		8.4.1607, Esbo gård
	34-37	Receipts		
3522	1-253	Cadastre		
3523	1-6	Miscellaneous	s	Tenala socken
	7-14	Miscellaneous	s	Pojo socken
	15-21	Miscellaneous	s	Lojo socken
	22-28	Miscellaneous	s	Sjundeå socken
	29-33	Miscellaneous	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	34-40	Miscellaneous	s	Esbo socken
3523a	1-11	Miscellaneous		Ransaknings längd
3524	1-42	Receipts	s	
	43-46	Miscellaneous	A	
	47-164	Receipts	s	

1606		1106 fol.	
327	Peder Andersson	District bailiwick 58 fol.	
3525	1-58	Bailiff's concept	
327	Mikael Larsson	District bailiwick 671 fol.	
3526	1-73	Bailiff's concept	
	74-75	Inventory s	
3527	1-89; 96-233	Cadastre	
	90-95	Miscellaneous A	
	234-240	Tenant farms	
	241-250	Tenant farms	
3528	1-6	Miscellaneous	
	7-12	Register on fines A	
	13-144	Receipts s	
	145	Mantals register s	
	146-149	Mantals register A	
	150-346	Receipts s	
321	Johan Jacobsson	District bailiwick 311 fol.	
3529	1-52	Bailiff's concept	
	2-3	Receipts s	
3530	1-7	Mantals register s	
	8-13	Mantals register s	
	14-16	Mantals register s	
	17-24	Mantals register s	
	25-29	Mantals register s	
	30-35	Mantals register s	
	36-42	Mantals register s	
	43-54	Mantals register s	
	55-78	Receipts s	
3531	1-139	Receipts s	
	140-143	Ecclesiastical rec. s, A	
	144-147	Ecclesiastical rec. s, A	
	148-153	Ecclesiastical rec. s, A	
	154	Receipts s	
	155-158	Ecclesiastical rec. s	
	159-161	Ecclesiastical rec. s	
	162-165	Ecclesiastical rec. s	
	166-170	Ecclesiastical rec. s, A	
	171-175	Ecclesiastical rec. s, A	
	176-181	Ecclesiastical rec. s, A	
329	Peder Hertzig	District bailiwick 66 fol.	
3532	1-49	Bailiff's concept	
	50-66	Receipts s	
1607		827 fol.	
327	Mikael Andersson	District bailiwick 277 fol.	
3533	1-66	Bailiff's concept	
3534	1-16	Ödes längd A	
	17-166; 168-1	Receipts s	
	167, 170	Register on fines A	
	171-173	Miscellaneous	
	174-177	Receipts s	
3534a	1-34	Miscellaneous	
329	?	District bailiwick 28 fol.	
3534b	1-28	Ödes längd	

327	Mikael Andersson		District bailiwick	220 fol.
3535	1-32	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	
3536	1-20	Receipts		
	21-24	Miscellaneous	s	
	25-146	Receipts	s	
	147-150	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1608. Helsinges socken
	151-152	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Anno 1608. Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
	153-154	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1608. Sibbo socken
	155-169	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Anno 1608. Borgå socken
	170	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1608. Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	171-176	Ecclesiastical rec.		Anno 1608. Pernå socken
	177-178	Register on fines	s, A	Anno 1608
	179-180	Inventory	s	12.9.1608
	181-188	Receipts	s	
321	Anders Dom		District bailiwick	302 fol.
3537	1-58	Bailiff's concept		Johannis 1607 – Johannis 1608
3538	1-244	Receipts	s	
1608				757 fol.
327	Mårten Jacobsson		District bailiwick	225 fol.
3539	1-41	Cadastre		
	42-47	Tenant farms		
3540	1-102	Receipts	s	
	103-104	Miscellaneous	s	
	105-118	Receipts	s	
	119-128	Ödes längd	s	
	129-136	Miscellaneous	s	
	137-138	Inventory	s	12.9.1608, Helsinges fårs gård
	139-140	Inventory	s	18.7.1609, Helsinges fårs gård
	141-148	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, Qto	Anno 1609, Helsinges socken
	149-151	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1609, Sibbo socken
	152-160	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Anno 1609, Borgå socken
	161-162	Tenant farms		Anno 1609
	163-178	Receipts	s	
321	Mårten Jöransson		District bailiwick	240 fol.
3541	1-55	Bailiff's concept		Johannis 1608 – 1609
3542	1-185	Receipts	s	
329	Erik Mikaelsson		District bailiwick	292 fol.
3543	1-10	Receipts	s	Johannis 1608 – 1609
	11-67	Bailiff's concept		
3544	1-225	Cadastre		

1609				1111 fol.
327	Jören Larsson	District bailiwick		507 fol.
3545	1-88	Bailiff's concept		Johannis 1609 – Johannis 1610
3546	1-10	Miscellaneous	A	
	11-28	Ödes längd	A	
	29-30	Miscellaneous	A	
	31	Register on fines	A	
	32-381	Receipts	s	
	382-383	Inventory	s	18.7.1609
	384-385	Inventory	s	13.8.1610
	386-390	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1610, Helsinge socken
	391-393	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1610(?), Sibbo socken
	394-404	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Anno 1610, Borgå socken
	405-411	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Anno 1610, Pernå socken
3546a	1-8	Tenant farms		
321	Nils Clemetsson	District bailiwick		286 fol.
3547	1-70	Main account		Johannis 1609 – Johannis 1610
3548	1-13	Receipts	s	
	14-17	Register on fines	s	
	18-19	Ödes längd	s	
	20-100	Receipts	s	
	101-102	Mantals register	s	
	103-104	Receipts	s	
	105-108	Mantals register	s	
	109-154	Receipts		
	155-156	Mantals register	s	
	157	Mantals register	s	
	158-165	Receipts	s	
3549	1-11	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Lojo socken
	12-15	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Sjundeå socken
	16-20	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Kyrkslätt socken
	21-24	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Esbo socken
	25-31	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Ingo socken
	32-36	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Karis socken
	37-38	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Ekenäs stad
	39-40	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Kisko bol (?)
	41-44	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Karislojo kapellgäll
	45-47r	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Pojo socken
	47v-51	Hjonelag längd	s, A	Tenala socken

329	Erik Jönsson	District bailiwick	318 fol.
3550	1-71	Main account	
3551	1-143	Receipts	s
	144	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	145-149	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	150-153	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	154-157	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	158	Register on fines	s, A
	159	Register on fines	s, A
	160-193	Receipts	s
	194-197	Miscellaneous	s
	198-201	Miscellaneous	s, A
	202-209	Miscellaneous	s, A
	210-216	Miscellaneous	s, A
	217-234	Miscellaneous	s, A
	235-239	Miscellaneous	s, A
	240-247	Receipts	s
			Lapträsk kapellgäll(?)
			Itis kapellgäll(?)
			Pyttis socken
			Ransaknings längd, Vederlax socken
			Ransaknings längd, Veckelax socken
			Ransaknings längd, Pyttis socken
1610			678 fol.
327	Anders Henriksson	District bailiwick	86 fol.
3552	1-40	Cadastre	N.B. page/folio numbering for this signum
	41-53	Tenant farms	
	54-86	Receipts	
321	Henrik Larsson	District bailiwick	280 fol.
3553	1-69	Main account	
3554	1-4	Register on fines	s
	5	Miscellaneous	s
	6-8	Miscellaneous	s
	9-10	Receipts	s
	11	Miscellaneous	s
	12-13	Ödes längd	s
	14-17	Miscellaneous	s, A
	18	Miscellaneous	s
	19-20	Miscellaneous	s
	21-211	Receipts	s
329	Erik Hansson	District bailiwick	312 fol.
3555	1-4	Miscellaneous	s
	5-59	Main account	
3556	1-36	Cadastre	
	37-57	Miscellaneous	
	58-74	Ödes längd	s, A
	75-133	Receipts	
3557	1-11	Ecclesiastical rec.	A
	12-120	Receipts	s
			Seal f. 71v
			Veckelax & Pyttis socknar
1611			552 fol.
327	Heine Jönsson Wilkenn(?)	District bailiwick	77 fol.
3558	1-14	Miscellaneous	s, A
	15-26	Ödes längd	s, A
	27-34	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	35-38	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	39-49	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	50-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	
	54-77	Miscellaneous	s, A
			Perno socken
			Sibbo socken
			Borgå socken
			Helsinge socken
			Hjonelag längder

321	Mårten Jöransson Grabbe	District bailiwick	242 fol.
3559	1-63	Main account	
3560	1-39	Cadastre	
3561	1-19	Receipts	
	20-23	Ödes längd	s
	24	Miscellaneous	
	25	Miscellaneous	A
	26	Miscellaneous	s
	27-31	Register on fines	s
	32-140	Receipts	s
329	Erik Mikaelsson	District bailiwick	233 fol.
3562	1-61	Main account	
3563	1-16	Receipts	
	17-34	Miscellaneous	s, A
	35-52	Ödes längd	s, A
	53-58	Miscellaneous	s, A
	59-60	Register on fines	s, A
	61-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	69-75	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	76-79	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	80-83	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	84	Inventory	A
	85-87	Inventory	A
	88-172	Receipts	s
			Folios 61-67 empty
			Veckelax socken
			Pyttis socken
			Itis kapellgäll
			6.8.1611
			4.8.1612
1612			486 fol.
327	Heine Jönsson Wilkenn	District bailiwick	147 fol.
3564	1-56	Main account	
	57-59	Miscellaneous	
	60-62	Receipts	
3565	1-33	Cadastre	
	34-38	Tenant farms	
	39-42	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	43-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	54-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	57-58	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	59-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	62-78	Ödes längd	
	79-85	Receipts	s
			Anno 1613, Helsinge socken
			Anno 1613, Borgå socken
			Anno 1613, Sibbo socken
			Anno 1613, Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
321	Anders Eriksson	District bailiwick	97 fol.
3566	1-52	Main account	
	53-54	Receipts	s
3566a	1-4	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	5-7	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	8-10	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	11-13	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	14-15	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	16-18	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	10-25	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	26-27	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	28-31	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	94-105	Miscellaneous	s, A
			Pojo socken
			Sjundeå socken
			Kyrkslätt socken
			Esbo kapellgäll
			Victis socken
			Lojo socken
			Karislojo kapellgäll
			Kisko kapellgäll
			N.B.: folio numbers jump from 31 to 94

329	Erik Hansson			District bailiwick	122 fol.
	3567 1, 5-57	Main account			
	2-4; 58-59	Receipts	s		
	3568 1-31	Cadastre	s		
	3569 1-32	Cadastre			
327	Heine Jönsson Wilkenn			District bailiwick	120 fol.
	3569a 1-120	Receipts	s	Anno 1611 & 1612	
1613					224 fol.
327	Heine Jönsson Wilkenn			District bailiwick	65 fol.
	3570 1-60	Main account			
	61-65	Receipts	s		
329	Erik Hansson			District bailiwick	159 fol.
	3571 1-41	Main account		Johannis 1613 – Johannis 1614	
	3572 1-31	Cadastre	s	Anno 1614	
	3573 1-50	Receipts	s		
	51-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Veckelax socken	
	57-58	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lappträsk kapellgäll	
	59-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Itis kapellgäll	
	62-67	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pyttis socken	
	68-82	Ödes längd	A		
	83-87	Receipts	s		
1614					429 fol.
327	Nils Jönsson			District bailiwick	301 fol.
	3574 1, 3-79	Main account		Johannis 1614 – Johannis 1615	
	2	Receipts	s		
	3575 1-30	Cadastre			
	31-39	Ödes längd	s		
	40-51	Miscellaneous	s		
	3576 1-2	Register on fines	s		
	3-12	Receipts	s		
	13-18	Miscellaneous	A		
	19-38	Receipts	s		
	39-40	Miscellaneous	s		
	41-110	Receipts	s		
	11-123	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Perno socken	
	124-135	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1615, Borgå socken	
	136-138	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Nurmis kapellgäll(?)	
	139-140	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Anno 1615, Sibbo socken	
	141	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		
	142-148	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken	
	149-171	Receipts	s		
321	Leonhard Bönnichen			District bailiwick	128 fol.
	3577 1-70	Main account			
	3578 1-58	Cadastre			

1615		526 fol.	
329	Anders Nilsson	District bailiwick 97 fol.	
3578a 1-2	Receipts	N.B.: Empty folios without folio numbers in this signum	
3-15	Ödes längd	A	
16-29	Miscellaneous	s, A	
30-32	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Vederlax socken
33-37	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Veckelax socken
38-40	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Itis kapellgäll
41-43	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pyttis socken
44-45	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1614
46	Register on fines	s	
Two fol.	Register on fines	s, A	Folios not numbered
47-95	Receipts	s	
327	Botvid Hansson	District bailiwick 148 fol.	
3579 1-62	Main account		
63-72	Tenant farms		
3580 1-35r	Cadastre	s	
35v-48	Tenant farms	s	
49-55	Ödes längd	s	
56-71	Miscellaneous	s	
72-76	Receipts	s	
321	Henrik Larsson	District bailiwick 281 fol.	
3581 1; 14	Receipts		
2-13; 15-66	Main account		
67-68	Register on fines	s	
69-74	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
75-79	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo kapellgäll
80-84	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
85-86	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
87-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
91-92	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo kapellgäll
93-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko socken
95-96	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Victis kyrkgäll
97-101	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
3582 1-180	Receipts	s	
1616		1332 fol.	
329	Anders Nilsson	District bailiwick 119 fol.	
3583 1-86	Receipts	s	
87-90	Miscellaneous	s, A	
91-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Vederlax socken
95-98	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1615, Lappträsk kapellgäll
99-104	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Veckelax socken
105-108	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Itis kapellgäll
109-112	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pyttis socken
113-114	Register on fines	s, A	
115-119	Receipts	s	

327	Botvid Hansson	District bailiwick	367 fol.
3584	1-13	Receipts	s
	14-78	Main account	
3585	1-36	Cadastre	s
	37-48	Tenant farms	
	49-66	Miscellaneous	s
3586	1-21	Miscellaneous	s, A
3587	1-47	Receipts	s
	48-49	Miscellaneous	A
	50-148	Receipts	s
	149-152	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	153-154	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	155-156	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	157-164	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A
	165-172	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	173-202	Receipts	s
			Helsinge socken
			Anno 1614. Sibbo socken
			Anno 1615. Mäntsälä kapellgäll
			Borgå socken
			Anno 1615, Pernå socken (?)
321	Leonhard Bönnichen	District bailiwick	756 fol.
	3588 1-47	Main account	
	3589 1-309	Cadastre	
	3590 1-50	Miscellaneous	s
		51-72	Miscellaneous
			s, A
	3591 1-6	Miscellaneous	
		7-28	Receipts
			s
		29-31	Miscellaneous
			s
		32-50	Receipts
			s
		51-56	Miscellaneous
			s
		57-66	Receipts
			s
		67-69; 71-75	Ödes längd
		70	Receipts
		76-78	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		79-83	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		84-87	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		88-93	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		94-95	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		95b-d	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		96-99	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		100-102	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		103-106	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		107-111	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		112-117	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		118-121	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		122-127	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		128-128b	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		129-132	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		133-136	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s, A
		137-140	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		141-144	Ecclesiastical rec.
			s
		145-155	Receipts
			s
	3592 1-2	Receipts	
		3-6	Register on fines
			s
		7-169	Receipts
			s
			Esbo socken
			Kyrkslätt socken
			Sjundeå socken
			Lojo socken
			Karislojo kapellgäll
			Esbo socken
			Pojo socken
			Kisko socken
			Tenala socken
			Anno 1617, Esbo socken
			Anno 1617, Kyrkslätt socken
			Anno 1617, Sjundeå socken
			Anno 1617, Lojo socken
			Anno 1616 & 1617, Karislojo kapellgäll
			Anno 1617, Esbo socken
			Anno 1617, Tenala socken
			Anno 1617, Pojo socken
			Anno 1617, Kisko socken

329	Heine Wilkenn	District bailiwick	90 fol.
3593 1-54	Main account		
55-62	Estate account		
63-64	Inventory	s	8.8.1616
65-68	Miscellaneous	A	
69-70	Receipts	s	
71-73	Miscellaneous	A	
74-79	Miscellaneous		
80-90	Receipts		
1617			242 fol.
327	Botvid Hansson	District bailiwick	103 fol.
3594 1-53	Main account		
54-56	Estate account		Vik ladugård
57-59	Inventory		1.4.1616, Vik Ladugård
60-67	Register on fines	s, A	
68-72r	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
72v-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Nurmå kapellgäll
79-80	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Mäntsälä kapellgäll
81-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken
91-96	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sibbo socken
97-103	Receipts	s	
321	Leonhard Bönnichen	District bailiwick	139 fol.
3595 1-40	Main account		
3596 1-5	Receipts	s	
6-13	Ödes längd	s	
14-18	Register on fines	s	
19-99	Receipts	s	

1618		932 fol.	
327	Botvid Hansson	District bailiwick 478 fol.	
3597	1-2; 5-6; 21-74	Main account	
	3-4; 8-20	Receipts	
	75-77	Inventory	s Vik ladugård
	80-83	Miscellaneous	
	84-101	Receipts	s
3597a	1-70	Receipts	s Anno 1617!
3598	1-35	Cadastre	
	36-47	Tenant farms	s
	48-53	Ödes längd	s
	54-60r	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pernå socken
	60v-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Nurmå kapellgäll
	62-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Anno 1619, Helsinge socken
	66-70; 73-77	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Borgå socken
	71-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	78-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Several parishes
	86-94	Tenant farms	A
	95-96	Miscellaneous	
	97-113	Miscellaneous	s
	114-115	Miscellaneous	
	116-131	Receipts	
	131	Ödes längd	
3599	1-63	Receipts	s
	64-67	Register on fines	s, A
	68-77	Miscellaneous	A
	78-83	Receipts	s
3599a	1-92	Receipts	s

321	Nils Sigfridsson	District bailiwick	454 fol.
3600 1-51	Main account		
52-56	Register on fines	s	
57-60	Inventory	s	4.7.1618, Esbo gård
61-79	Estate account		Esbo gård
80-82	Receipts		
3601 1-83	Cadastre		
84-85	Miscellaneous	s, A	
3602 1-7	Miscellaneous		
8-27	Receipts		
28-29	Miscellaneous	s	
30-37	Miscellaneous	s, A	
38-97	Receipts	s	
98-101	Miscellaneous	A	
102-177	Receipts	s	
178-181	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
182-185	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Seal cut out. Pojo socken
186-189	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko socken
190	Receipts		
191-192; 194	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo kapellgäll
193	Receipts	s	
195-200	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lojo socken
201-202	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sjundeå socken
203-206	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
207-208	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1619, Esbo
209-210	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Victis
211-226	Receipts	s	
227-229	Mantals register		Esbo gård
230	Miscellaneous		Lönings register
231-287	Receipts	s	

1619	481 fol.
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327	Lars Markusson	District bailiwick	141 fol.
3603 1-41	Main account		
3604 1-39	Cadastre	s	
40-53	Tenant farms		
54-58	Ödes längd	s	Borgå län
59-63	Ödes längd	A	
64-69	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
70-79	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken
80-81	Ecclesiastical rec.		Mäntsälä kapellgäll
82-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sibbo socken
86-87	Ecclesiastical rec.		Nurmo kapellgäll
88-93	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
94-98	Miscellaneous	s	
99-100	Miscellaneous	s	

Nyland	District bailiwick	18 fol.
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3604a 1-16	Ödes längd		
17-18	Receipts	s	

321			District bailiwick	282 fol.
3605	1-50	Cadastre	s	Anno 1619(?)
	51-171	Cadastre		Anno 1620
	172-175	Miscellaneous	s	Anno 1619 & 1620
	176-181	Receipts	s	
3605a	1-16	Receipts	s	
	17-19	Miscellaneous	s, A	
	20-30	Ödes längd	s, A	
	31-69	Receipts	s	
	70-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Vederlax socken
	73-78	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Veckelax socken
	79-81	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Itis kyrkogäll
	82-88	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pyttis socken
	89-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lapträsk(?) kapellgäll
	91-101	Receipts	s	
329			Heine Wilkenn	District bailiwick 40 fol.
3606	1-40	Main account		
1620 443 fol.				
327			Lars Markusson	District bailiwick 130 fol.
3607	1-41	Main account		
3608	1-38	Cadastre		
	39-52	Tenant farms		
	53-56	Ödes längd		
	57-62	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
	63-64	Ecclesiastical rec.		Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	65-68	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sibbo socken
	69-72	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
	73-89	Receipts	s	
Nyland			District bailiwick	27 fol.
3608a	1-24	Ödes längd		Borgå och Raseborgs län
	25-27	Receipts	s	
329			Heine Wilkenn	District bailiwick 232 fol.
3608b	1-8	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Veckelax socken
	9-16	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pyttis & Elimä socken
	17-18	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lapträsk(?) kapellgäll
	19-70	Receipts	s	
3609	1-35	Main account		
	36-40;	Receipts		
	41-107	Account		Several accounts, 1620 & 1621
	108-109	Receipts		
3610	1-32	Cadastre	s	
3610a	1	Register on fines	s, A	
	2-4	Miscellaneous	s, A	
	5-21	Ödes längd	s, A	
321			Didrik Svensson	District bailiwick 54 fol.
3610b	1-10	Miscellaneous	s	Boskaps längd
	11-16	Miscellaneous	s	Boskaps längd
	17-28	Miscellaneous	s	Boskaps längd
	29-54	Miscellaneous	s	Boskaps längd

1621		407 fol.
327	Henrik Andersson	District bailiwick 238 fol.
3611	1-31; 34-50	Main account
	32-33	Receipts
3612	1-8	Miscellaneous s
	9-45	Cadastre s
	46-51	Tenant farms
	52-54	Miscellaneous s
	55-60	Receipts s
	61-65	Ecclesiastical rec. Anno 1622, Helsinge socken
	66-72	Ecclesiastical rec. s Borgå socken
	73-81	Ecclesiastical rec. s Pernå socken
	82-84	Ecclesiastical rec. s Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	85-155	Receipts s
	156-164	Miscellaneous
	165	Receipts s
3613	1-23	Receipts
321	Jöns Jönsson	District bailiwick 51 fol.
3614	1-51	Main account
329	Heine Wilkenn	District bailiwick 118 fol.
3615	1-23	Account
	24	Receipts
3616	1-32	Cadastre s
3616a	1-27	Miscellaneous
	28-52	Ödes längd
	53-56	Miscellaneous
	57-62	Receipts
1622		464 fol.
327	Henrik Andersson	District bailiwick 241 fol.
3617	1-46	Account
3618	1-15	Receipts s
	16-17; 22-23	Ecclesiastical rec. s Anno 1621, Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
	18-21	Ecclesiastical rec. s Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
	24	Receipts
	25-26	Ecclesiastical rec. Anno 1621 & 1622, Sibbo socken
	27-29	Receipts s
	30-40	Miscellaneous s
	41-76	Cadastre s
	77-90	Tenant farms
	91	Receipts
	92-98	Ecclesiastical rec. s Borgå socken
	99-105	Ecclesiastical rec. s Pernå socken
	106-111	Ecclesiastical rec. s Helsinge socken
	112-157	Receipts s
	158-161	Miscellaneous s, A
	162-165	Receipts s
	166-179	Register on fines s, A
	180-195	Receipts s
321	Olof Clemetsson	District bailiwick 47 fol.
3619	1-47	Main account

329		Heine Wilkenn		District bailiwick	176 fol.
3620	1-30	Main account		Daniel Nilssons räkenskap (häradskrivare)	
	31-46	Receipts	s		
	47-54	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Pyttis socken
	55-56	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Anno 1623, Lappträsk kapellgäll	
	57-78	Receipts	s		
	79-80	Miscellaneous			
	81-96	Receipts	s		
3621	1-80	Miscellaneous			
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1623					497 fol.
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327		Mats Henriksson		District bailiwick	242 fol.
3622	1-49	Main account			
	50-61	Tenant farms		No folio numbering	
3623	1-92	Receipts	s		
3623a	1-13	Miscellaneous	s		Helsinge socken
	14-28	Miscellaneous	s		Sibbo socken
	29-61	Miscellaneous	s		Borgå socken
	62-82	Miscellaneous			Pernå socken
	83-88	Miscellaneous			
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321		Nils Jönsson		District bailiwick	52 fol.
3624	1-44; 47-48	Main account			
	45-46; 49-52	Receipts	s		
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329		Heine Wilkenn		District bailiwick	203 fol.
3625	1-38	Main account			
	1-49	Receipts			
3626	1-35	Cadastre			
	36-49	Receipts			
	50	Miscellaneous	s		
	51-56	Miscellaneous	A		
	57-73	Ödes längd	s, A		
	74-75	Register on fines	s, A		
	76-79	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Vederlax socken
	80-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Veckelax socken
	86-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Itis kapellgäll
	91-97	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Pyttis socken
	98-101	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Lappträsk kapellgäll
	102-154	Receipts	s		
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1624					491 fol.
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327				District bailiwick	167 fol.
3627	1-10; 12-13	Account			
	11	Receipts	s		
	14-27	Account			
	28-58r	Cadastre			
	58v-69	Tenant farms			
	70-98	Receipts			
	99-104	Miscellaneous	s		
	105-112	Ödes längd	s		
	113-120	Miscellaneous	s		
	121-122	Register on fines	s		
	123-128	Register on fines	s, A		
	129-163	Receipts	s		
	164-167	Ödes längd	s		No folio numbers

321		Anders Andersson		District bailiwick	75 fol.
3628	1-29	Account			
	30-64	Account			
	113-114	Miscellaneous		Folio numbering jumps from 64 to 113	
	115-117	Miscellaneous			
	118-119	Miscellaneous			
	119a-d	Receipts			
329		Heine Wilkenn		District bailiwick	108 fol.
3628a	1-23	Bailiff's concept			
	24-48	Miscellaneous	s		
	->	Receipts	s	Folios 27-29; 31-32; 37; 39-41; 43-44 & 46	
3628b	1-22	Additional taxes	s		Pyttis socken
	23-26	Additional taxes	s		Lappträsk kapellgäll
	27-40	Additional taxes	s		Veckelax socken
	41-47	Additional taxes	s		Itis kapellgäll
	48-60	Additional taxes	s		Vederlax socken
Nyland				District bailiwick	141 fol.
3628c	1-14	Miscellaneous	s		Karis socken
	15-24	Miscellaneous	s		Tenala socken
	25-32	Miscellaneous	s		Ingå socken
	33-39	Miscellaneous	s		Pojo socken
	40-47	Miscellaneous	s		Sjundeå socken
	48-63	Miscellaneous	s		Lojo socken
	64-76	Miscellaneous	s		Lojo socken
	77-83	Miscellaneous	s		Karislojo kapellgäll
	84-98	Miscellaneous	s		Kyrkslätt socken
	99-108	Miscellaneous	s		Borgå socken
	109-112	Miscellaneous	s		Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	113-117	Miscellaneous	s		Pernå socken
	118-125	Miscellaneous	s		Sibbo socken
	126-138	Miscellaneous	s		Helsinge socken
	139-141	Miscellaneous	s		Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
1625					428 fol.
327		Claes Andersson		District bailiwick	213 fol.
3629	1-36	Account			
3630	1-3	Miscellaneous			Avkortnings längd
	4-7	Receipts			
	8-40	Cadastre			
	41-53	Tenant farms			
	54-61	Miscellaneous	A		
	62-128	Receipts	s		
	129-132	Miscellaneous	A		
	133	Miscellaneous			
	134-141	Miscellaneous	s		
	142-151	Ödes längd	s, A		
	152-163	Receipts			
	164-167	Ödes längd			
	168-175	Register on fines	s		
	176-177	Receipts	s		

321	Tomas Larsson?		District bailiwick	196 fol.
3631	1-35	Account		
3632	1-4	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Tenala socken
	5-6	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pojo socken
	7-8	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kisko socken
	9-14	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken
	15-17	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo kapellgäll
	18-19	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken
	20-22	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken
	23-25	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Esbo socken
	26-28	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Victis socken
	29-32	Register on fines	s	
	33-52	Receipts	s	
	53-60	Miscellaneous		
	61-62	Miscellaneous	s	
	63-65	Receipts		
	66-67	Miscellaneous		
	68	Miscellaneous		
	69-75	Receipts		
	76-77	Miscellaneous		
	78-115	Receipts	s	
3633	1-38	Miscellaneous		
	39-40	Miscellaneous		
	41-46	Miscellaneous		
329	Heine Wilkenn		District bailiwick	19 fol.
3634	1-18	Account		
	(17b)	Receipts	s	Fragment
1626				801 fol.
329	?		District bailiwick	47 fol.
3634a	1-47	Miscellaneous		
327	Mats Henriksson		District bailiwick	210 fol.
3635	1-33	Account		
	34-39	Register on fines	s, A	
	40-49	Ödes längd	A	
	50-59	Miscellaneous		
	60-63	Miscellaneous		
	64-98a	Receipts	s	
	99-102	Miscellaneous		
	103-108	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Helsinge socken
	109-112	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
	113-114	Ecclesiastical rec.		Nurmo kapellgäll
	115-126	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken
	127-128	Ecclesiastical rec.		Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	129-136	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
	137-142	Ödes längd	s	
	143-151	Receipts	s	
3636	1-41	Cadastre	s	
	42-56	Tenant farms		
	57-58	Miscellaneous		

321	Tomas Larsson	District bailiwick	544 fol.
3637	1-17	Receipts	
	18-42	Account	
	43-46	Miscellaneous	
	47-48	Receipts	
	49-52	Miscellaneous	
	53-73	Receipts	s
	74	Miscellaneous	
	75-77	Receipts	s
	78	Miscellaneous	s
	79-135	Receipts	s
	136-138	Miscellaneous	
	139-141	Receipts	s
	142-144	Miscellaneous	
	145-160	Receipts	s
	161-166	Miscellaneous	A
	167-177	Receipts	s
3637a	1-367	Miscellaneous	

1627 459 fol.

327	Mats Henriksson	District bailiwick	222 fol.
3638	1-27	Account	
	28-38	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Borgå socken
	39-40	Ecclesiastical rec.	Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	41-42	Ecclesiastical rec.	Nurmo kapellgäll
	43-48	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Helsinge socken
	49-52	Ecclesiastical rec.	Sibbo socken
	53-60	Ecclesiastical rec.	Pernå socken
	61	Miscellaneous	A
	62-70	Ödes längd	s
	71-80	Miscellaneous	s
	81-82	Receipts	
	83-85	Miscellaneous	
	86-124	Receipts	s
3639	1-47	Account	
	14	Receipts	
3640	1-41	Cadastre	s
	42-49	Tenant farms	
	50-51	Receipts	

321		Henrik Jöransson		District bailiwick	237 fol.
3641	1-30	Account			
3642	1-21	Account			
	22-25	Miscellaneous			
	26-27	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Tenala socken
	28-31	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Pojo socken
	32-33	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Sjundeå socken
	34-39	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Lojo socken
	40-41	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Karislojo kapellgäll
	42-44	Ecclesiastical rec.	A		Kisko socken(?)
	45-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Victis socken(?)
	48-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Kyrkslätt socken
	52-55	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Esbo socken
	56-114	Receipts	s		
	115-126	Ödes längd			
	127-138	Miscellaneous			
	139-143	Miscellaneous	A		
	144-149	Receipts	s		
3643	1-39	Miscellaneous			
	134-138	Miscellaneous		Misplaced. Folio numbering jumps to 134	
	120-121	Miscellaneous		Misplaced. Folio numbering again jumps	
	122-133	Receipts	s		
<hr/>					
1628					199 fol.
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327		District bailiwick		63 fol.	
3644	1-63	Miscellaneous			
321		Lars Henriksson		District bailiwick	136 fol.
3645	1-27	Account			
	28-37	Miscellaneous	A		
	38-45	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Lojo socken
	46-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Karislojo kapellgäll
	48-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Kyrkslätt socken
	52-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Tenala socken
	54-55	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Victis socken
	56-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Sjundeå socken
	58-61	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Esbo kapellgäll
	62-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A		Kisko bol
	66-67	Register on fines	A		
	68-73	Miscellaneous			
	74-79	Ödes längd			
	80-136	Receipts	s		
<hr/>					
1629					295 fol.
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327		Lars Markusson		District bailiwick	69 fol.
3646	1-12	Account			
	13-19	Ödes längd	s		
	20-25	Receipts			
	26-30	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Pernå socken
	31-39	Ecclesiastical rec.			Borgå socken
	40-44	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Helsinge socken
	45-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	48-67	Account			
	68	Miscellaneous	s		
	69	Receipts			

321		Anders Larsson		District bailiwick 226 fol.	
3647	1-43	Account			
	44-49	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Sjundeå socken
	50-55	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Kyrkslätt socken
	56-59	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Esbo socken
	60-65	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Tenala socken
	66-71	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Pojo socken
	72-75	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Karislojo socken
	76-77	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Kisko bol
	78-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Lojo socken
	86-89	Ecclesiastical rec.	s		Enemä bol(?)
	90-97	Register on fines			
	98-119	Miscellaneous	s		
	120-127	Ödes längd			
	128-133	Miscellaneous			
	134-226	Receipts	s		
1630				339 fol.	
327				District bailiwick 55 fol.	
3648	1-2	Miscellaneous			Borgå och Pernå socknar
	3-7	Miscellaneous	s		Helsinge socken
	8-12	Miscellaneous	s		Helsinge socken
	13-16	Miscellaneous	s		Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
	17-26	Miscellaneous	s		Sibbo socken
	27-35	Miscellaneous	s		Borgå socken
	36-37	Miscellaneous	s		Mäntsälä kapellgäll
	38-40	Miscellaneous	s		Lapträsk kapellgäll
	41-53	Miscellaneous	s		Pernå socken
	54-55	Miscellaneous			

321	Anders Larsson	District bailiwick	284 fol.
3649	1-30	Account	
	31-60	Account	
	61-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Tenala socken
	65-67	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Pojo socken
	68-69	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A Kisko socken
	70-74	Ecclesiastical rec.	A Karislojo kapellgäll
	75-82	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Lojo socken
	83-86	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Sjundeå socken
	87-90	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Kyrkslätt socken
	91-94	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Esbo socken
	95-96	Ecclesiastical rec.	s
	97-108	Ödes längd	
	109-112	Register on fines	A
	113-141	Receipts	s
	142-149	Ödes längd	s
	150-151	Miscellaneous	
	152-160	Miscellaneous	
	161-162	Miscellaneous	
3650	1-75	Cadastre	
3651	1-5	Miscellaneous	s Esbo socken
	6-12	Miscellaneous	s Kyrkslätt socken
	13-17	Miscellaneous	s Sjundeå socken
	18-24	Miscellaneous	s Lojo socken
	25-28	Miscellaneous	s Karislojo socken
	29-33	Miscellaneous	s Karis socken
	34-37	Miscellaneous	s Ingo socken
	38-41	Miscellaneous	s Pojo socken
	42-43	Miscellaneous	s Kisko bol
	44-47	Miscellaneous	s Tenala socken
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1631			394 fol.
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327	Nils Joensson	District bailiwick	168 fol.
3652	1-4	Miscellaneous	
	5-38	Account	
	39-58	Receipts	s
	59-63	Miscellaneous	
	64-85	Receipts	s
	86-96	Ödes längd	
	97-102	Miscellaneous	
	103-108	Miscellaneous	
3653	1-37	Cadastre	
	38-45	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Borgå socken
	46-52	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Pernå socken
	53-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Helsinge socken
	58	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
	59-60	Ecclesiastical rec.	s Mäntsälä kapellgäll

321	Olof Joensson		District bailiwick	226 fol.
3654 1-32	Account			
33-43	Ödes längd			
44	Register on fines	A		
45-54	Ödes längd	A		
55-60	Receipts	s		
61-63	Miscellaneous	s, A		
64-88	Receipts	s		
89-92	Miscellaneous			
93-110	Receipts	s		
111-116	Miscellaneous	A		
117-120	Receipts	s		
121-140	Ödes längd			
141-143	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Tenala socken	
144-145	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Pojo socken	
146	Ecclesiastical rec.		Kisko bol	
147-148	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Karislojo socken	
149-153	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Lojo socken	
154-155	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sjundeå socken	
156-160	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Kyrkslätt socken	
161-163	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Esbo socken	
164-170	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Två bol i Vichtis socken	
3655 1-56	Cadastre			
<hr/>				
1632				360 fol.
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327	Nils Joensson		District bailiwick	219 fol.
3656 1-82	Account			Page numbering
83-103b	Receipts	s		
104-113	Ödes längd	s, A		
114-116	Register on fines	s, A		
117-120	Ödes längd	s		
121-130	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken	
131-138	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken	
139-142	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Helsinge socken	
143-146	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sibbo socken	
147	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Mäntsälä kapellgäll	
148-149	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Nurmijärvi kapellgäll	
150-153	Miscellaneous			
154-163	Miscellaneous			
164-176	Receipts			
3657 1-32	Account			
33-44	Miscellaneous			
3658 1-39	Cadastre			

321	Olof Joensson	District bailiwick	141 fol.
3659 1-16	Account		
17-18	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Vichtis socken
19-22	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Karislojo kapellgäll
23-30	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Lojo socken
31-34	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Kyrkslätt socken
35-36	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pojo socken
37-38	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Tenala socken
39-40	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Esbo socken
41-43	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sjundeå socken
44-48	Ödes längd	s	
49-54	Miscellaneous		
55-109	Receipts	s	
110	Miscellaneous	A	
111	Ödes längd	A	
112-115	Miscellaneous		
116-137	Receipts		
138-141	Ödes längd	s	

1633 301 fol.

327	Henrik Falk	District bailiwick	170 fol.
3660 1-44	Account		
45-54	Receipts		
55-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken
65-70	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Pernå socken
71-74	Ecclesiastical rec.		Helsinge socken
75-76	Ecclesiastical rec.		Mäntsälä kapellgäll
77-80	Miscellaneous		
81-86	Ödes längd	s	
87-92	Miscellaneous		
93-100	Receipts		
101-104	Register on fines	A	
105-113	Receipts		
114-115	Miscellaneous	s	
116	Receipts		
117-120	Miscellaneous	s	
121-134	Miscellaneous	s	
3661 1-36	Cadastre		

321	Lars Falk	District bailiwick	131 fol.
3662 1-35	Account		
36-37	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Tenala socken
38-39	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Kisko bol
40-41	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Vichtis socken
42-47	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lojo socken
48-49	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Kyrkslätt socken
50-51	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Esbo socken
52-53	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sjundeå socken
54-55	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Karislojo kapellgäll
56-57	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Pojo socken
58-59	Ödes längd		
60-61	Register on fines	s, A	
62-65	Ödes längd	s	
66-69	Miscellaneous		
70-111	Receipts	s	
112-115	Ödes längd	s	
116-131	Receipts	s	

1634 499 fol.

327	Henrik Falk	District bailiwick	254 fol.
3663 1-40	Account		
41-49	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Borgå socken
50	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Mäntsälä kapellgäll
51-55	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Helsinge socken
56-60	Ecclesiastical rec.		Pernå socken
61-64	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Sibbo socken
65-66	Ecclesiastical rec.	s	Nurmijärvi kapellgäll
67-71	Miscellaneous		
72-77	Ödes längd	s, A	
78	Miscellaneous	s	
79-82	Ödes längd		
83-90	Miscellaneous		
91-109	Receipts		
110-116	Miscellaneous	A	
117-129	Receipts	s	
130-133	Miscellaneous	s	
3663a 1-28	Miscellaneous	A	
3664 1-33	Cadastre		
34-43	Tenant farms		
44-81	Account		
82-93	Miscellaneous		

327	Lars Falk	District bailiwick	245 fol.
3665 1-68	Account	Page numbering (1-68) instead of folio numbering	
76-77	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Tenala socken
78-79	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Pojo socken
80-81	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Två bol i Vichtis socken
82-83	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Kisko socken
84-85	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Karislojo kapellgäll
86-89	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Lojo socken
90-91	Ecclesiastical rec.	s, A	Sjundeå socken
92-93	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Kyrkslätt socken
94-95	Ecclesiastical rec.	A	Esbo socken
96-100	Miscellaneous		
99	Receipts		
101-102	Miscellaneous	A	
103-114	Ödes längd		
115-138	Receipts		
139-145	Miscellaneous		
140-145	Receipts		Double folio numbering
146-149	Receipts		
150-151	Ödes längd		
152-163	Receipts		
164	Register on fines		
165-166	Miscellaneous		
167-174	Receipts		
175-178	Miscellaneous	s, A	
179-201	Receipts	s	
3666 1-29	Account		
3667 1-50	Cadastre		